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Milestone 20.6

Methodological and data infrastructure report on children

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In preparing our report, we considered all comments and suggestions received. However, we take full responsibility for the contents of the report.

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of live or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

Contents

1.	Aim and scope	5
2.	The proposed structure of IPOLIS	9
3.	Policy context: the evolution of child mainstreaming process within the EU	13
4.	Data infrastructure	15
5.	The proposed set of indicators	19
5.1	Material living conditions	19
5.1.1	Poverty	20
5.1.2	Material deprivation	20
5.1.3	Housing	21
5.1.4	Poverty and social exclusion	22
5.2	Labour market attachment and work-life balance	24
5.2.1	Labour market attachment	24
5.2.2	Work-life balance	24
5.3	Education	26
5.4	Health and risk behaviours	28
5.4.1	Health status	28
5.4.2	Health behaviours	29
5.4.3	Risk behaviours	31
5.5	Social connectedness and civic participation	35
5.5.1	Family and peer relationships	35
5.5.2	Civic participation	37
5.6	Environmental quality and physical safety	38
5.6.1	Environmental quality	38
5.6.2	Physical safety	39
6.	Recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructure and the way forward	47
	Bibliography	55

The Innovative tools and protocols for poverty and living conditions research work package (WP20)

The work package is part of the 'Poverty and living conditions' pillar. Its objectives (among others) are:

- to synthesise and make accessible data and knowledge in a structured form that backs comparative research on social policies, improves infrastructure to reach vulnerable groups at risk of poverty;
- to organise indicators and research results in a theoretical frame, with the aim of avoiding bottlenecks and temptations to carry on purely data driven research on poverty and living conditions;
- to carry on purely data driven research on poverty and living conditions.

Nine specific vulnerable groups in total are identified:

- easy-to-reach groups: (a) children (0-17 years), (b) youth (15-30 years) and (c) older people (65+ years);
- hard-to-identify groups: (d) migrants, (e) Roma, (f) travellers;
- hard-to-reach groups: (g) institutionalised people, (h) undocumented immigrants and (i) homeless people.

Tasks to be carried out within the WP:

- task 20.1: building an integrated poverty and living conditions indicator system (IPOLIS);
- task 20.2: optimising the use of census micro-data to analyse and monitor poverty and living conditions at the territorial level in Europe;
- task 20.3: identifying priorities for future data collection.

Related deliverables and milestones:

- D20.1 Conceptual report for IPOLIS;
- D20.2 Complete IPOLIS data base for the vulnerable groups.

1. Aim and scope

The present methodological and data infrastructure report aims at providing a full proposal for the Child module of the Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS). We are doing this by following the general framework set up by the IPOLIS Concept Paper (Gábos and Kopasz 2014; henceforth referred as ICP). Hereby, we briefly summarise the most important characteristics of IPOLIS, along with touching upon the dilemmas we faced during the preparation of the ICP.

i. IPOLIS aims to improve infrastructure for analysing and monitoring the situation of vulnerable groups

IPOLIS, as one of the main outcomes of the Poverty and Living Conditions pillar of the InGRID project (see short description in the box), is aimed to improve infrastructure for analysing and monitoring the situation of most vulnerable groups. It is conceived to serve as a resource for various user groups (researchers, policy makers at different levels, NGO experts, journalists, students, etc.) to:

- monitor the situation of children, the youth and the elderly in the field of poverty, living conditions and quality of life;
- observe relationships between indicators and to detect cross-country patterns according to selected measures.

ii. Quality of life is chosen as the core concept of IPOLIS

The ICP set up a theoretical framework for the indicator system to be elaborated, which is based on the concept of Quality of Life (QoL). Quality of life was defined as a multi-dimensional concept comprising objective measures, and people's perceptions of these factors (economic, social, etc.), that is, subjective measures of objective substances (Joint

Research Centre – IPSC 2012: 17). The QoL concept, as proposed in the ICP, includes objective living conditions (including material and non-material aspects such as income, material deprivation, quality of housing, education, health, etc.), and subjective perceptions about these factors (e.g. subjective income position, self-reported health status).

iii. IPOLIS will rely on the existing data infrastructure, mainly on the European Statistical System

Considering the above listed aims of IPOLIS, the indicator system needs to be data driven. Accordingly, the structure of the database and the indicator selection process are and will be conditioned by the availability of data. The European Statistical System (ESS) data (regular Eurostat coordinated surveys, European Quality of Life Survey - EQLS, Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement - SHARE) will gain priority in selecting specific indicators. Besides these data sources, IPOLIS will rely on other survey data generally used by similar initiatives (e.g. European Social Survey - ESS, OECD Programme for International Student Assessment - PISA, Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children - HBSC, etc.).

iv. IPOLIS will link the three vulnerable age groups

The ICP reviewed the already available international (EU as well as non-EU) and national indicator systems that are thematically related to IPOLIS (i.e. poverty, quality of life and well-being indicator systems). With very few exceptions, prior indicator system initiatives relate either to one specific age group (e.g. children, older people, etc.) or to the population as a whole. When building IPOLIS, however, we faced the challenge to develop an indicator system structure, which is able to handle three different age groups (children, the youth and the elderly) within a single frame. Therefore, in designing and building IPOLIS and the related database, we needed to:

- ensure a coherence of the indicator system structure at the level of domains, components and subcomponents;
- set up direct linkages between groups at indicator level that allow for a comparative assessment of their relative position - primarily according to the dimensions of poverty and material living conditions;
- consider that each stage of life cycle has its own characteristics and thus we need to pay special attention to age-group specific problems.

A set of indicators, referred to as *overarching* indicators in the ICP, characterizes all three groups. Ideally, these measures should have the same definition and should be produced on the same data source. The application of these criteria is facilitated by the fact that vulnerable groups in IPOLIS are defined by age. Household level indicators, like household income and material living conditions,

The Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS)

IPOLIS will be the core outcome of the work package on innovative tools and protocols for poverty and living conditions research of the InGRID project. Work package 20 is part of the 'Poverty and living conditions' pillar of the project and integrates the research activity within the pillar. The aim of the work package is to build a platform to improve infrastructure for monitoring, analysing and evaluating the situation of the most vulnerable groups. The **integrated poverty and living conditions indicator system (IPOLIS)** will be produced for the easy-to-reach vulnerable groups: children, youth and older people. However, the flexible nature of the proposed structure and implementation plan of IPOLIS allows for the inclusion of other vulnerable groups (e.g. disabled persons, migrants), when they will be coherently identifiable in a large data infrastructure, and robust indicators will be ready for production. For the hard-to-identify and hard-to-reach vulnerable groups protocols will be developed for the creation of a database in a later stage.

obviously meet these criteria. On the contrary, there are indicators that could also be relevant for all three age groups (e.g. perceived general health or physical activity), but there is no single data source to produce them. In addition, another group of potential indicators can be relevant for two vulnerable groups. For example, this is the case with risk behaviour indicators, which are significant for both children and youth, or with employment rate which is an important indicator for both the youth and the elderly.

v. IPOLIS will cover all EU-28 Member States for a time period between 2004 and 2013

Being a strongly data driven database, we needed to clearly define the main parameters of IPOLIS. *Country coverage:* IPOLIS is planned to cover the EU-28. The inclusion of Iceland, Norway and Switzerland in the database may be considered. These countries are part of the Eurostat Statistical System, with regular and EU compatible data collection standards. Some practical considerations also support this choice: it is easier to develop a larger frame from the beginning of the project than in a later phase, when the indicator database has already been set up.

Time period: 2004 (major EU enlargement) - 2013 (or latest year available at the time of data upload in the database).

vi. Age group specific dilemmas

When building IPOLIS, we have faced some additional challenges that are specific to the different age groups. In what follows, we discuss those that relate to the children portfolio of IPOLIS.

The project proposal refers to children as those being aged 0-17. The age boundaries of childhood are clearly set in the existing practice of monitoring child poverty and child well-being: all major works in the field consider children as those aged 0 to 17 years inclusive, in line with the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Children (UN 1989). At the same time, child well-being indicator systems frequently include indicators for which the reference population steps over the age of 17 years. Early school leaving, for which the reference population is the 18-24 years old (TÁRKI 2011, Social Protection Committee 2012), or ‘Youth NEET¹ rate’ with the age coverage of 15-19 years (OECD Doing Better for Children, Social Protection Committee 2012) can be examples of this. These indicators can be parts of youth indicator systems in the same way - and indeed they are (see e.g. the EU Youth Strategy dashboard set of indicators). Since IPOLIS is an initiative that aims to integrate children and the youth in one indicator system, we needed to make a decision in these cases. As a rule of thumb, we decided to include those indicators for which the reference population steps over the age boundary of 17 years in the Youth module of IPOLIS. This is the case, for example, with teenage pregnancy, early school leaving and the youth NEET rate.

The concepts of ‘quality of life’ and ‘well-being’ alike focus on present conditions. In the case of children, however, it is important to complete the QoL approach with a future oriented view, considering the intergenerational aspect of poverty and social exclusion, as well as the increasing evidence on the efficiency of early interventions (e.g. Heckman and Masterov 2004). In practice this means that during the indicator selection process we put a strong emphasis on indicators that best predict adulthood outcomes, like labour market participation or earning potential.

To summarize, the present paper aims to:

- provide a full indicator proposal for the children portfolio of IPOLIS;
- prepare an indicator fiche for each and every proposed indicator;

¹ NEET is abbreviation for Not in Employment, Education or Training.

- make ready the set up of the Child module of the IPOLIS database for all countries and all years specified by the ICP (including main indicators as well as breakdowns and confidence intervals where relevant).

The paper is organised in the following way. In Chapter 2, we present the structure of IPOLIS based on the ICP. From Chapter 3 onwards, we narrow down the discussion to children's quality of life. First, the policy context of monitoring children's quality of life is outlined in Chapter 3. In Chapter 4, we take an inventory of the data infrastructure we can use to provide input for the Child module of IPOLIS. Chapter 5, the core chapter of the paper, is devoted to the selection of indicators measuring the different aspects of children's quality of life. In order to select the most appropriate indicators for each domain and component of IPOLIS, we review all the potential relevant indicators that meet the criteria of indicator selection laid down in ICP. Finally, Chapter 6 provides recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructure.

2. The proposed structure of IPOLIS

We present the proposed structure (domains, components and sub-components) of IPOLIS in Table 1. Six domains of QoL have been identified in the ICP, including material living conditions, labour market attachment and work-life balance, education and training, health and risk behaviours, social connectedness and civic participation, physical environment and safety. Beyond these six domains, policy and context indicators are also part of the indicator set.

Table 1 Proposed structure of IPOLIS

	DOMAIN	COMPONENT	SUB-COMPONENT
1.	MATERIAL LIVING CONDITIONS	1.1 Poverty	a. Extent of poverty b. Depth of poverty c. Persistence of poverty
		1.2 Material deprivation	
		1.3 Housing	a. Overcrowding b. Housing costs c. Housing deprivation
		1.4 Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)	
2.	LABOUR MARKET ATTACHMENT AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE	2.1 Labour market attachment	a. Employment b. Precarious employment c. Self-employment d. Unemployment e. Labour market attachment of hhs
		2.2 Work-life balance	a. Work and leisure b. Work and care
3.	EDUCATION AND TRAINING	3.1 Access to and quality of education	a. Early childhood education b. Educational attainment c. Lifelong learning
		3.2 Educational achievement	a. Achievement in basic skills b. Early school leaving
4.	HEALTH AND RISK BEHAVIOURS	4.1 Health status	a. Objective health status b. Subjective health status
		4.2 Health behaviours	a. Physical activity b. Obesity
		4.3 Risk behaviours	a. Smoking b. Alcohol consumption c. Illicit drugs d. Teenage births e. Psychological distress f. Suicide
5.	SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS AND CIVIC PARTICIPATION	5.1 Family and peer relationships	a. Family relationships b. Peer relationships
		5.2 Civic participation	a. Voting/voter turnout b. Volunteering and group membership c. Internet use
6.	ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY AND PHYSICAL SAFETY	6.1 Environmental quality	
		6.2 Physical safety	

Some smaller changes have been made to the initial state of IPOLIS outlined in the ICP, though, without affecting the basic structure of the indicator system. These are as follows:

- We decided to withdraw the ‘income, expenditure and wealth’ component of the ‘material living conditions’ domain from the originally proposed structure, with the intention to place the related indicators (e.g. average household income, final average consumption expenditure per adult equivalent) into the domain ‘context indicators’. Although they themselves can be seen as measures

of quality of life, they better indicate the differences in the standards of living across countries, providing context information to interpret country differences in outcomes.

- The 'poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)' component has been added to IPOLIS after the completion of the ICP. The EU2020 poverty and social exclusion indicator is a composite measure of three indicators, which belongs to three different components under the 'material living conditions' and the 'labour market attachment and work-life balance' domains. We decided to have this indicator as a separate component instead of including it under one of the three constituent components (poverty, material deprivation, and labour market attachment) since it is a head indicator in the European Commission's monitoring process (see later in Section 5.1).
- The 'risk behaviours' component of the 'health and risk behaviours' domain initially included a 'bullying' sub-component. However, since in a later stage we opted for measuring being bullied (bullying victimization) instead of bullying, it seemed reasonable to regroup it under the 'family and peer relationships' component of 'social connectedness and civic participation' (see later in Section 5.5.1).
- Further, two sub-components of the 'civic participation' component, namely 'volunteering' and 'group membership' have been merged into one due to the lack of separate data (see later in Section 5.5.2).
- Similarly, the two sub-components of the 'environmental quality' component have been merged on account of lack of separate data on outside air pollution (see later in Section 5.6.1).

The domains of IPOLIS (and specifically the six QoL domains) are comparable to most of the recent well-being reports, like the 2009 Stiglitz-Sen-Fitoussi Commission report or the 2011 OECD How's Life initiative. However, there are some notable differences (ICP: 20-21).

- A major difference is the dimension 'health'. In general, health is more pronounced in IPOLIS. Health behaviours and risk behaviours are separate components in IPOLIS, while they are neglected in both the SSFC Report and the OECD How's Life. At the same time, 'health' is also a key dimension in the child well-being indicator system outlined in UNICEF IRC 7 (and also in the succeeding ones, like OECD Doing Better for Children, Bradshaw and Richardson 2009 and SPC 2012). The importance of health and risk behaviours is not only great for the children but also for the youth. Further, declining health can have a detrimental effect on older people's quality of life.
- Another difference relates to the dimension of 'governance'. This is a separate dimension both in the SSFC Report and in the OECD How's Life initiative. Although, the content of this dimension is different, they have 'active citizenship' (voter turnout) in common. Similarly, IPOLIS includes 'civic participation' as a component of the domain 'social connectedness and civic participation'. However, further elements of the dimension 'governance' (e.g. trust, satisfaction with public services) are not covered by IPOLIS.
- Another key difference between the proposed domains of IPOLIS and of the above mentioned indicator systems lies in the domain 'subjective well-being' or 'overall life satisfaction'. This flows from the differing concepts of well-being and QoL. Well-being indicator systems generally include the domain (or component) 'subjective well-being'. This is also true of child well-being indicator systems (UNICEF IRC 7 and also in Bradshaw and Richardson 2009). At the same time, IPOLIS does not include life satisfaction as domain (or even as component) of QoL. The main reason for this is that the concept of QoL, as defined in ICP, comprises subjective measures only if they refer to subjective assessment of objective factors. This criterion does not meet in case of overall life satisfaction, since it is a subjective measure per se. In addition, empirical reasons also support the omission of overall life satisfaction. As it is argued in UNICEF IRC 11, subjective well-being overlaps with other dimensions of child well-being, and is therefore best considered as a separate measure in its own right (rather than as one component of an indicator system) (UNICEF 2013: 38).

- Finally, as opposed to prior initiatives, the proposed indicator system includes policy and context indicators as separate domains that are structurally distinguished from domains that include outcome indicators of QoL. Policy indicators serve to better understand the relationship between social processes and government interventions, and their development partly relies on inputs from activities within the Social Policy pillar of the InGRID project. Context indicators help better understanding outcomes. This report focuses on the six domains of QoL, while policy and context indicators will be discussed in detail in a separate report.

3. Policy context: the evolution of child mainstreaming process within the EU

The political framework relates directly to European cooperation on social protection and social inclusion (the Social Open Method of Coordination, henceforth the Social OMC), as part of which the European Union has expressed its strong political commitment to combating child poverty and promoting well-being among children, regardless of their social background. We can summarize the main steps of the child mainstreaming policy process in the European Union as follows.

1989:

The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) was adopted by the UN. The UN CRC incorporates a full range of rights for children.

2005:

- The March 2005 EU Presidency Conclusions, which explicitly referred to child poverty and announced the European Youth Pact.
- The Luxembourg Presidency initiative on 'Taking Forward the EU Social Inclusion Process', which called explicitly for the mainstreaming of children and for the adoption of at least one child well-being indicator at the EU level.

2006:

- The 2006 March Presidency Conclusions, which called for more action to eradicate child poverty in the Member States.
- The adoption of the Commission's communication entitled 'Towards an EU Strategy on the Rights of the Child, Communication from the Commission'.
- The streamlining of the Social OMC, since when there has been a more systematic consideration of several well-being indicators for children. The child well-being slot is not filled in yet, according to the 2009 review of the Social OMC indicator portfolio.

2007:

The establishment of the EU Task-Force on Child Poverty and Child Well-Being within the frame of the Social Protection Committee.

2008:

- The formal adoption in January of the report and recommendations of the EU Task-Force (2008) report² by all Member States and the Commission, and the incorporation of these into the EU acquis in this area.
- The inclusion in National Strategy Reports of child poverty as a key priority in 24 Member States, many of which set specific targets for its reduction.

2 ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=2049&langId=en.

2009:

The TÁRKI-Applica report, which was presented to the Commission and to the Indicators Sub-Group of the Social Protection Committee and published in 2010³.

2010:

The Belgian Presidency conference on child poverty and the book on the roadmap for Europe 2020 of Frazer, Marlier and Nicaise (2010) commissioned by the presidency, which set out a 'roadmap' for recommendations to fight child poverty⁴.

2011:

The Hungarian EU Presidency, which submitted a Council Conclusion entitled 'Tackling child poverty and promoting child well-being' to the Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs Council (EPSCO) on 17 June for adoption.

2012:

- The *SPC Advisory Report to the European Commission on tackling and preventing child poverty, promoting child well-being* (henceforth referred as SPC 2012 or SPC report). The SPC report presented a proposal for a portfolio of child specific indicators, which sets the present EU monitoring framework of children's situation. It adopted a holistic approach and went beyond the monetary aspects of child poverty. By taking further the policy priorities expressed by the 'Who cares? Roadmap for an EU Recommendation on child poverty' of the Belgian presidency in September 2010, the SPC report is based on three pillars: access to adequate resources and support to households, access to quality services, and children's participation.
- The Cyprus High Level Presidency Conference on Investing in children: Preventing and tackling child poverty and social exclusion, promoting children's well-being on 18-19 October 2012 in Lefkosia (Nicosia, Cyprus).

2013:

The European Commission launched the Social Investment package (European Commission 2013), including the recommendation of investing in children, adopted later on by EPSCO (Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs) Council of Member States.

In addition, a series of reports and calls of EPSCO Council of Members States in favour of tackling child poverty and social exclusion, were produced within the framework of initiatives funded under the PROGRESS stream, as part of the Social OMC. These included reports by the EU Network of Independent Experts on Social Inclusion, the European poverty networks (e.g. Eurochild, the European Anti-Poverty Network - EAPN, the European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless - FEANTSA and the European Social Network - ESN), various peer reviews and other exchange projects.

3 <http://www.tarki.hu/en/research/childpoverty/>.

4 http://www.mi-is.be/sites/default/files/doc/EN-Report%20child%20poverty_BAT.pdf.

4. Data infrastructure

In this chapter, we take an inventory of data sources that may serve as an infrastructure for building and sustaining the child module of IPOLIS. We consider cross-country comparative surveys that are conducted on samples representing the total population living in individual households or only children. Additionally, in some cases surveys conducted in the adult population (individuals aged 15 or 16 and over) can also be relevant for indicators characterising the later stage of childhood. Obviously, we prefer datasets that span long time periods and thus provide the opportunity to analyse trends.

As the ICP pointed out, the wide set of indicators that constitutes the monitoring framework of the Social OMC can be a starting point of building IPOLIS, since its different indicator portfolios are based on solid, flexible and standardised data infrastructure. However, there is an increasing need to improve the poverty and living conditions research infrastructure in order to keep-up with the progress that takes place in the policy arena.

Table 2 provides an overview of the datasources we considered as relevant for the selection of indicators of children's QoL. The table shows the main parameters of the datasets, including whether the dataset is part of the European Statistical System (ESS) or not, which is a relevant issue, considering the sustainability of IPOLIS. The status and main characteristics of these datasources can be summarised as follows.

- In general, surveys and data collections that are representative for either the total or the adult population are numerous and cover several quality of life domains and components that constitute IPOLIS, as presented in ICP (Table 6 on pages 38-40). The EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) covers all private households and all children living in them, and thus constitutes a unique source for producing household level material living condition indicators. However, the role of adult surveys is marginal for the child module of IPOLIS. While child-focused surveys generally take a large sample of a specific age cohort, in adult surveys the age bracket of 15-17 year olds is usually not large, and the number of observations may reduce the robustness of indicators. It makes more sense, however, to extract some indicators from adult surveys (for individuals aged 15+ or 16+) for the Youth module of IPOLIS. In this way, by applying breakdown by age groups we may gain interpretable results for young people aged 15-19.
- Most of these adult surveys are part of the ESS, however, their status varies largely in terms of the starting year and periodicity. For example, the EU-SILC is conducted on a yearly basis, while the EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) are even more frequently and both sources cover the whole post-enlargement period. This means that the domains 'material living conditions' and 'labour market attachment and work-life balance' can be adequately covered in IPOLIS. In addition, the EU-SILC can provide important indicators for some other domains, like 'environmental quality and physical safety'.
- Child-centered surveys are not part of the ESS and are relatively weak in country coverage. Not only countries are missing, but in a few cases (like Belgium or the United Kingdom in the Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children – HBSC, or the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study - PIRLS surveys) countries are represented by only one or more regions, implying an obvious restriction to the comparability of the results.

Overall, a large cross-country comparative infrastructure is available for children, but with important gaps, as recently highlighted by a report prepared by Richardson (2013) on surveys of children. Among the flaws of this infrastructure we can notice here the followings.

- Some domains of children's quality of life are well covered by a set of surveys. Foremost, 'education and training', 'health behaviour and risk behaviour' should be mentioned here. (Administrative data for young children's health status are also abundant.) However, we have identified data gaps in the domain 'environmental quality and physical safety' (see later in Chapter 5).
- Children under age of 9 are not (or only poorly) represented in (mostly school-based) surveys.
- Important groups of children in need (migrant children, institutionalized children, street children, etc.) are completely missing from well-being focused data collections.

Table 2 An overview of potential data sources for the child module of IPOLIS

Data source	ESS status	Age coverage	Time period, periodicity	Country coverage	Domains covered
Children					
<u>ESPAD</u> European School Survey Project on Alcohol and Other Drugs	Not part of the ESS	Children aged 15-16	1995-, every four years	39 countries in total in 2011, out of which 24 are EU-28 members, plus Iceland and Norway. Belgium was represented by Flanders, while Germany by 5 Bundesländer.	Substance use
<u>HBSC</u> Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children	Not part of the ESS	Children aged 11, 13, 15	1983-, every four years	43 countries and regions in total, with all EU-28 included except Cyprus. Belgium and the UK are represented by regions (French and Flemish part of Belgium, and England, Scotland and Wales, respectively). Iceland, Norway and Switzerland are also included.	Health and risk behaviours, family and peer relations, life satisfaction
<u>ICCS</u> International Civic and Citizenship Education Study	Not part of the ESS	Children at their eighth grade (not younger than 13.5 years)	2008/2009	22 out of EU-28, plus Norway and Switzerland. Belgium is represented by Flanders, while UK by England	Conceptual understandings and competencies in civic and citizenship education.
<u>PISA</u> OECD Programme for International Student Assessment	Not part of the ESS	Children aged 15	2000-, every three years	OECD countries, including all EU-28 but Cyprus.	Competencies in reading, mathematics and science
<u>TIMSS</u> Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study	Not part of the ESS	Children at their fourth and eighth grades	1995-, every four years	63 countries and regions, out of which 21 are EU-28 Member States in 2011. Belgium is represented by Flanders, while UK by England and Northern Ireland. Norway is also included.	Competencies in mathematics and science
<u>PIRLS</u> Progress in International Reading Literacy Study	Not part of the ESS	Children at their fourth grade	2001-, every fifth years	48 countries and regions, out of which 23 are EU-28 Member States in 2011. Belgium is represented by Wallonia, while UK by England and Northern Ireland. Norway is also included.	Competencies in reading
Total population					
<u>EU-SILC</u> Statistics on Income and Living Conditions	Part of the ESS	Total population living in private households	2003-, yearly	EU-28, Iceland, Norway	Income, poverty, social exclusion and living conditions
Adult population					
<u>EU-LFS</u> Labour Force Survey	Part of the ESS	15 and over in private households	1983-, yearly	EU-27 (Croatia from 2012), Iceland, Norway and Switzerland	Labour market

5. The proposed set of indicators

This chapter is aimed to provide methodological underpinnings of the selection of indicators measuring the different aspects of children's quality of life. The chapter is organised according to the domains and components/sub-components of IPOLIS as presented in Chapter 2. However, only those components/sub-components of IPOLIS are discussed here which are relevant for children. We proceed in the following way: first, we review the potential indicators for each domain and component/subcomponent and the datasources from which indicators can be extracted. A separate table has been compiled for each domain to show the indicators that are used by the existing indicator systems, including the EU and other international initiatives (UNICEF IRC 7, OECD Doing Better for Children, and TÁRKI 2011), as well as, some of the national ones we have had access to. The latter ones will be useful in making recommendations in Chapter 6. Finally, based on theoretical considerations as well as empirical evidences we attempt to select the most appropriate indicators for each components/sub-components. Also, we suggest breakdowns for each indicator. A summary table (Table 9) of selected indicators can be found at the end of this chapter.

5.1 Material living conditions

There is a wide literature on the measurement of material living conditions in general, and on the measurement of poverty and material deprivation in particular. Boarini and d'Ercole (2006) distinguishes between monetary and non-monetary measures on the one hand, and between indirect (input-based) methods using relative thresholds to distinguish between poor and non-poor and direct (outcome-based) methods using absolute thresholds on the other hand. According to this classification, relative income poverty measures are monetary and input based, while material deprivation indicators are considered as non-monetary and outcome-based measures, though such a clear distinction better serves analytical aims rather than reflecting the reality. In terms of measurement, there is also a strong ambition to reflect on the multidimensional nature of the problem. Among these initiatives we may note those trying to capture the capabilities approach of Sen (2000) (e.g. Headey 2006 for Australia), the consistent poverty approach proposed by Whelan, Nolan and Maitre (2006) or the ambition of the European Commission to set up a target for the fight against poverty and social exclusion (European Commission 2010).

By providing an indication on the available resources and observed outcomes or contrarily, on the shortage or inadequacy of them, material well-being is usually at the core of the cross-country comparative and national level indicator systems. This is mainly the case with all monitoring systems in the field of poverty and living conditions operated by the European Commission (Atkinson et al. 2002, Marlier et al. 2007). Specifically for children, the availability of material resources is seen as prerequisite to achieve good outcomes not only in childhood, but also in adulthood. This is why material living conditions are distinguished part of the overall structure (e.g. SPC 2012, OECD Doing better for Children, UNICEF IRC 7 and 11, TÁRKI 2011). IPOLIS follows this way, also taking into consideration the indicator of fight against poverty and social inclusion target set by the Europe 2020 strategy, which relies not only on the relative income measure of poverty, but also on subindicators of severe material deprivation and low work intensity. The four components of the domain 'material living conditions' include (i) poverty; (ii) material deprivation, (iii) housing, and (iv) poverty and social exclusion (see Table 3).

5.1.1 Poverty

- Indicators of income poverty are widely used as measures of lack of financial resources at household level and of social exclusion in terms of inadequacy of resources to participate in society (Atkinson et al. 2002), or as measures of resources required to achieve well-being (Boarini and d'Ercole 2006). Income-based indicators are monetary and indirect measures of poverty, according to the typology set up by Boarini and d'Ercole (2006).
- These measures are among those with the longest experience and best data infrastructure, not only at national level, but in a cross-national comparative frame as well. The methodology of collecting data on income at household level and individual level is harmonised now across developed countries (Canberra Group 2001, 2011). Presently, at the European level, the EU-SILC provides the data infrastructure to supply all indicators based on income in a comparable way across all Member States. EU-SILC, started in 2003, replaced the European Community Household Panel (ECHP), which lasted for 8 years, between 1994 and 2001. EU-SILC represents a powerful instrument for analysing the economic and social state of the EU as well as a growing number of non-EU European countries (Atkinson and Marlier 2010: 22). This infrastructure provides a regular and reliable basis to produce indicators of poverty not only for the overall population, but also for sub-groups like children⁵.
- The relative income poverty concept allows for a set of indicators that are closely related to each other conceptually and methodologically, as well as in terms of data requirement (e.g. Foster, Greer and Thorbecke 1984, Decanq et al. 2013). Of the many indicators of relative income poverty, the European Union agreed on the use of the at-risk-of-poverty rate, defined as the share of those individuals, whose equivalent household income does not exceed 60% of the median. In addition, a set of other indicators are part of the social inclusion indicator portfolio of the monitoring system. These additional income-based measures include dispersion of poverty risk near the poverty threshold (set at 40, 50, and 70% of the median income), at-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a moment in time, as well the poverty gap and the persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate.
- The OECD Doing Better for Children initiative includes one measure of poverty: the share of children in poor homes, which coincides in practice with the at-risk-of-poverty rate calculated at the 50% of the median equivalent household income (being a standard protocol for establishing the poverty threshold within the OECD). The same indicator is included in the UNICEF IRC 7 (see Table 3).
- In the indicator selection for the 'poverty' sub-component, we basically follow the practice of the European Commission as reflected by the Social OMC portfolio of indicators and the SPC (SPC 2012). The 'extent of poverty' sub-component is represented by the at-risk-of-poverty rate (AROP) and the at-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fix moment in time (2005). The first indicator is the lead measure of the relative income poverty concept, while the second one better represents the absolute poverty concept, by fixing the poverty threshold estimated for a given year, which is adjusted later only with the price index. The 'depth of poverty' is represented by the relative median poverty gap indicator, measuring the median normalised distance of individuals who live at risk of poverty. Finally, the persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate captures the risk of children to stay for a longer time in a low-income status.

5.1.2 Material deprivation

- Material deprivation is a complementary approach to the income-based measurement of poverty and social exclusion. Indicators of material deprivation are non-monetary and outcome-based measures. Material deprivation refers to the lack of material goods, financial strain and to the

⁵ For a more detailed analysis on the role of EU-SILC in producing poverty and income inequality indicators see Atkinson and Marlier (2010).

inability of individuals to live a decent life (Boarini and d’Ercole 2006). Usually, measures of material deprivation are composite indices that cover more than one dimension (e.g. financial strain, lack of durables, in some cases even housing deprivation) and consist of several individual items. At country level, material deprivation rate is more strongly correlated with the national income (or with the living standards) than relative income poverty measures are.

- Indicator development initiatives related to material deprivation have been accelerated during the last period, as part of the effort to go beyond the strictly income-based measures of poverty and social exclusion. An indicator of material deprivation (developed by Guio 2009) was adopted by the European Commission and it was made part of the Social OMC portfolio of indicators in 2009. Presently, this indicator of material deprivation used by the European Commission is under revision, while a child-specific material deprivation indicator is also under development and suggested for regular monitoring (Guio, Gordon and Marlier 2012).
- As part of the Child module of IPOLIS, we selected the severe material deprivation rate, the inability of making ends meet and the educational deprivation as representing the ‘material deprivation’ component. Severe material deprivation provides information on children’s deprivation building on household level items. We selected it against the material deprivation indicator due to the fact that it is part of the EU2020 fight against poverty and social exclusion measure, which is a lead indicator in policy monitoring at EU level. Inability of making and meets is a subjective evaluation of the household’s financial situation.⁶ It should have been classified under the ‘income poverty’ component as well. However, empirical analyses suggest that it’s correlation with material deprivation is stronger than with relative income poverty; and it reflects not only the level of material resources a household possesses, but also its adequacy to ensure a decent standard of living. Similarly to the severe material deprivation rate, this measure also strengthens the coherence of IPOLIS, being available for all the three age groups from the same datasource (EU-SILC).
- In addition, we also included the child-specific material deprivation indicator (Guio, Gordon and Marlier 2012), assuming that this indicator development will receive green line from the European Commission to become part of the Social OMC indicator portfolio.⁷ This measure adds to the one based on household level items only, by relying on child-specific individual items as proxies for the allocation of resources between adults and children within the household. Still, this information is collected from the household reference persons, not from the children themselves.
- Finally, educational deprivation (included in the OECD Doing Better for Children initiative, as well as in the UNICEF IRC 7) also represents a child-specific measure, indicating the resources available for children’s learning. Derived from the PISA survey, educational deprivation is defined as the share of 15-year-old children reporting less than five educational items out of seven items among 15-year-olds in the school population.

5.1.3 Housing

- Housing is either missing from most of the reviewed child well-being indicator systems or is underrepresented compared to other domains. The OECD Doing Better for Children initiative includes housing as a separate domain, albeit together with the local environment, which is considered a separate domain in IPOLIS. The domain ‘housing and environment’ in the OECD initiative includes two measures: overcrowding and poor environmental conditions. Housing indicators are not part of the well-being indicator system proposed by the UNICEF IRC 7.

6 Thinking of your household’s total income, is your household able to make ends meet, namely, to pay for its usual necessary expenses? Answer categories on a six-category scale: 1 – with great difficulty, 6 – very easily.

7 Considering the ongoing methodological work on material deprivation in general (see Gordon, Guio and Marlier 2012, Guio and Marlier 2013), and on persistent material deprivation in particular (see D’Ambrosio 2013), there is the opportunity to split this component (similarly to the income poverty component) in subcomponents of extent, depth and persistency of material deprivation when the indicator development process ends up with the adoption of indicators as part of Social OMC.

- Housing indicators are not child-centered, they are collected at household level. The best source to produce such indicators for the EU Member States, is the EU-SILC, although HBSC and EQLS also provides information on housing conditions that could be suitable for indicator development. EU-SILC has the advantage of large sample sizes, the full coverage of children aged 0-17, and the indicator development work done by Eurostat on this datasource.
- The 'housing' component of IPOLIS consists of three subcomponents, each of them including one indicator: (i) overcrowding (overcrowding rate), (ii) housing costs (housing cost overburden rate), and (iii) housing deprivation (housing deprivation rate). Our choice of indicators coincides with the recommendations of the SPC (2012). Overcrowding rate combines information on the number of rooms within the flat or house with basic demographic information on sex and age of household members. The measure reflects the living standards of the more affluent countries from Northern and Western Europe, and therefore it strongly differentiates between the Member States. Housing deprivation indicators are very rarely used; of the reviewed initiatives, only the SPC (2012) and (in a more indirect way) the America's Children initiative include them.

5.1.4 Poverty and social exclusion

- We decided to have the poverty and social exclusion indicator as a separate component in IPOLIS (as mentioned in Chapter 2) instead of including it under one of the three constituent components (poverty, material deprivation, and labour market attachment) since it is a head indicator in the European Commission's monitoring process. Also, this measure is suitable to serve as an overarching indicator across the three age-group modules of IPOLIS.
- Along with the adoption of the Europe 2020 strategy on smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, the European Commission set a portfolio of indicators, which serves as headline targets to monitor the most relevant processes that are in the focus of the strategy. Within this set, the inclusiveness of economic growth is represented by the fight against poverty and social exclusion indicator. This measure is composed of three indicators. An individual is considered to be at risk of poverty or social exclusion if he or she is at-risk-of-poverty, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity.⁸
- The use of social indicators in framing a Europe-wide monitoring system in the field of social inclusion is strongly linked to the start of the Lisbon era (Atkinson et al. 2002). The system of indicators adopted by the Laeken European Council in 2001 was further developed and extended during the 2000s within the frame of the Open Method of Coordination on Social Protection and Social Inclusion (European Commission 2006; European Commission 2009; Marlier et al. 2007). The Europe 2020 fight against poverty and social exclusion policy target is based on individual measures that have been either part of the Laeken set of indicators from the very beginning (like the at-risk-of-poverty rate) or have been developed during the recent years on the basis of a single datasource, the EU-SILC (see, for example, Guio 2009, for the material deprivation indicator, and Ward and Özdemir 2013 and Corluy and Vandenbroucke 2013 for the low work intensity indicator). The adoption of the composite indicator of multidimensional poverty was an outcome of a political coordination motivated by the different views and interests of the Member States (Maître et al. 2013) rather than a measurement tool representing a clear European social policy programme.

⁸ For the detailed methodology of the composite and the individual indicators see <http://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=10421&langId=en>.

Table 3 Summary table of indicators related to the domain 'material living conditions'

Components and sub-components	EU	OTHER INTERNATIONAL	NATIONAL
Poverty			
Extent of poverty	At-risk-of-poverty rate (0-17) (OMC SIP, OP, SPC) Dispersion of child poverty risk around the poverty threshold (SPC) At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time (2005) for children (SPC)	OECD: children in poor homes IRC 7: relative income poverty TÁRKI: at-risk-of-poverty rate, dispersion around the poverty threshold	US: Children in poverty (AC: 0-17; CWI: 0-18) Wales: Relative child poverty, Absolute child poverty, Severe child poverty, Out-of-work poverty, In-work poverty, Fuel poverty New Zealand: Proportion of dependent children under 18 years with net-of-housing-cost household incomes below selected thresholds
Depth of poverty	Relative median poverty risk gap (OMC SIP, OP, SPC)	TÁRKI: relative median poverty gap	-
Persistency of poverty	Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate (0-17) (OMC SIP, SPC)	TÁRKI: persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate	Wales: Persistent child poverty
Material deprivation			
	Material deprivation rate (OMC SIP); Severe material deprivation rate (0-17) (SPC)	OECD: Educational deprivation IRC 7: children reporting low family affluence, children reporting few educational resources, children reporting fewer than 10 books in the home TÁRKI: material deprivation rate, severe material deprivation rate, educational deprivation	Wales: Material deprivation and low income combined
Housing			
Overcrowding	Overcrowding (OMC SIP)	OECD: overcrowding TÁRKI: overcrowding rate	US: Households with children ages 0–17 reporting shelter cost burden, crowding, and/or physically inadequate housing (AC) Wales: overcrowding (Living in Wales) New Zealand: Household crowding
Housing costs	Housing costs (0-17) (OMC SIP); Housing cost overburden (SPC)	TÁRKI: Housing cost overburden	US: Households with children ages 0–17 reporting shelter cost burden, crowding, and/or physically inadequate housing (AC)
Housing deprivation	Severe housing deprivation (SPC)		US: Households with children ages 0–17 reporting shelter cost burden, crowding, and/or physically inadequate housing (AC)
Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)			
	At risk of poverty or social exclusion of children (breakdown of the Europe 2020 poverty and social exclusion headline target)	-	-

Abbreviations

AC – America's Children: Key National Indicators of Well-Being

CWI – Child and Youth Well-Being Index

IRC 7 – UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (2007)

OECD – OECD Doing Better for Children (2009)

OMC – Portfolio of Indicators for the Monitoring of the European Strategy for Social Protection and Social Inclusion (2009)

OP – Overarching Portfolio

SIP – Social Inclusion Portfolio

SPC – SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (2012)

TÁRKI – TÁRKI (2011)

New Zealand – Children and Young People

Wales – Children and Young People's Monitor

5.2 Labour market attachment and work-life balance

5.2.1 Labour market attachment

- The 'labour market attachment' component of IPOLIS is organised in five sub-components: (i) employment, (ii) precarious employment, (iii) self-employment, (iv) unemployment, and (v) labour market attachment of households. The Child module of IPOLIS discusses labour market attachment of households, while the remaining four are part of the Youth module.
- In the reviewed cross-country child indicator systems, labour market attachment of households is measured either by the proportion of children living in jobless households, or by the proportion of children living in households with low work intensity (see Table 4). The first indicator, defined as children living in households in which no one of working age is in employment, is already used at the EU level to monitor social inclusion in the Member States. The source of this indicator is EU-LFS, which defines employment as 'being in work for at least one hour during the reference week of the survey'. The second indicator is based on another concept and a different datasource. A child is considered to live in a household with low/very low work-intensity if the value of the work-intensity indicator that characterises the household is below 0.2. (A work intensity of 1 refers to households in which all working age adults are working full time over the whole year; and a work intensity of 0 refers to households in which none of the working age adults have worked over a whole year.) The indicator is based on EU-SILC data, and is now used (for the overall population) as an individual indicator on which the EU 2020 poverty target is based. An important difference between the two measures of labour market attachment of parents is in the definition of employment. The EU-LFS measure (and the EU-SILC equivalent) is based on the International Labour Organization (ILO) definition of employment, which takes one hour a week as being the criterion for whether someone is employed or not. The work-intensity measure is based on self-assessment of the respondent whether he or she was employed or not in a particular month, and also whether being employed was his or her main activity (as opposed to being unemployed or inactive).
- Labour market attachment of parents in IPOLIS is measured by the percentage of children living in households with work intensity below 0.2. Evidence suggests that 0.2 is a reasonable figure to take in that in many countries the risk of poverty associated with a household work intensity of between 0 and 0.2 is more than the risk for 0 work intensity (Ward and Ozdemir 2013: 15).

5.2.2 Work-life balance

- The component 'work-life balance' consists two sub-components ('work and leisure' and 'work and care'), of which only 'work and care' is relevant for children.
- As can be seen from Table 5, the 'work and care' component of the domain 'labour market attachment' is measured by two different groups of indicators. The first group of indicators seeks to grasp the employment effect of parenthood and/or child care (e.g. difference between employment rate among people living in households without children and with at least one child aged 0-6; or employees in part time as % of total employees, taken because of care for children). The other group of indicators measures the share of children cared for (or not cared for) in formal arrangements, albeit, the individual indicators differ both in content and age coverage of children. Although, these indicators also give some indication of the extent to which child care services allow parents to work, they focus on child care services as an end in themselves. Childcare provides an opportunity for children to develop better social skills in pre-school settings and to benefit from care by professionals in formal and less formal (but socially organised) care institutions. Therefore, the accessibility and quality of childcare services are important aspects that contribute to child well-being (TÁRKI 2011).

- Data on the percentage of children who benefit from formal care arrangements⁹ are available from EU-SILC by age groups. There is a lack of data, however, on the quality of formal childcare arrangements. To measure the component ‘work and care’, IPOLIS will include the share of children (under the age of 3 years) cared for in formal arrangements.
- The indicators that seek to measure the employment impact of parenthood/child care can be extracted from EU-LFS, and are included in the SPC (2012) as context indicators. These indicators, however, can be considered more as indicators of the labour markets than measures of children’s QoL, and thus, IPOLIS will not cover them.

Table 4 Summary table of indicators related to the domain ‘labour market attachment and work-life balance’

Components and sub-components	EU	OTHER INTERNATIONAL	NATIONAL
Labour market attachment			
Employment	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Precarious employment	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Self-employment	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Unemployment	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Labour market attachment of hhs	Share of children living in low work intensity hhs (SPC);	IRC 7: children in households without an employed adult TÁRKI: share of children in low work intensity (EU-SILC); share of children in jobless households (EU-LFS)	US: Percentage of children ages 0–17 living with at least one parent employed year round (AC; CWI) Wales: The number of children living in workless households (Annual Population Survey) New Zealand: Proportion of children under 15 without a parent in paid work
Work-life balance			
Work and leisure	Not relevant for children		
Work and care	Share of children cared for (by formal arrangements other than the family) (SPC); Employees in part time (as % of total employees) due to child care (SPC: context indicator); Difference in pp between employment rate among people without and with children aged 0-6 (SPC: context indicator)	TÁRKI: share of children (0-2) not in formal child care (EU-SILC)	US: Primary child care arrangements for children ages 0–4 with employed mothers (AC); Percentage of children ages 3–6, not yet in kindergarten, in center-based care arrangements (AC); Child care arrangements for grade school children ages 5–14 with employed mothers (AC); Percentage of children ages 3–4 enrolled in PreKindergarten (CWI)

Abbreviations

AC – America’s Children: Key National Indicators of Well-Being
 CWI – Child and Youth Well-Being Index
 IRC 7 – UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (2007)
 OECD – OECD Doing Better for Children (2009)
 OMC – Portfolio of Indicators for the Monitoring of the European Strategy for Social Protection and Social Inclusion (2009)
 OP – Overarching Portfolio
 SIP – Social Inclusion Portfolio
 SPC – SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (2012)
 TÁRKI – TÁRKI (2011)
 New Zealand – Children and Young People
 Wales – Children and Young People’s Monitor

⁹ Formal arrangements are defined as the following services: pre-school or equivalent, compulsory education, centre-based services outside school hours, a collective crèche or another day-care centre, including family day-care organised/controlled by public or private structure.

5.3 Education

- Education in general, and access to quality education and educational achievement in particular are not only measures of present QoL, but also strong predictor of later adult outcomes in the field of labour market participation and earning potential (e.g. Heckman and Masterov 2004), and therefore that of intergenerational mobility and intergenerational transmission of poverty, too (OECD 2005).
- The data infrastructure related to the ‘education and training’ domain is relatively large and beyond administrative data includes three child-centered cross-country comparative surveys, specifically aimed at covering educational achievement in basic skills in an internationally comparative frame: PIRLS, TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) and PISA. PIRLS and TIMSS sample children by grade (4th grade), while PISA by age (15 years). Some issues related to sampling, cross-country comparability and methodology are discussed by Richardson (2012).
- The ‘education and training’ domain of IPOLIS is organised in two components: ‘access to and quality of education’ and ‘educational achievement’ (see Table 5). The first component, composed of three sub-components (‘early childhood education’, ‘educational attainment’, and ‘lifelong learning’), provides information on the institutional aspects of the education system. Access to early childhood education and care (ECEC) is the only indicator within the Child module. This shortage of child measures is due to the fact that potential indicators of educational attainment will be included in the Youth module. The reason for this, as mentioned before (under Section 2), is that the most relevant indicators (like upper secondary education attainment) refer to the 15-19 age group, and are observed at the age of 18-19.
- The inclusion of the ECEC access indicator is of major importance. The early ages of childhood and especially the early years between 0-2 are crucial for children's healthy cognitive, emotional, behavioural, physical and social development and this is where the mid- and long-term returns of investment many times outweigh the cost (SPC 2012: 20-21). Parents and family members have primary responsibility for their children and the effect of family background and parenting on the development of the child is strong. However, high quality ECEC can contribute to a large extent to this process and can support and complement home based learning and social experiences. Accordingly, ECEC can play an important role in reducing social inequalities and guaranteeing equal opportunities to children. These institutions may help break the transmission of disadvantage across generations and afford all children the opportunity to reach their full potential (SPC 2012: 21). It would improve to a large extent the monitoring of early ages if measures of quality of ECEC quality, of different child developmental outcomes (e.g. physical health and well-being, cognitive skills, emotional maturity, social competence) and of family satisfaction could complete the indicator of access to this type of service.
- The second component, comprising of two sub-components (‘achievement in basic skills’, ‘early school living’), includes indicators of skills that strongly predict success or failure, paths to live as a full member of the society or being excluded along one or more dimensions. These indicators bridge the institutional frame with vulnerabilities in adulthood, like marginalized labour market positions, inadequate income, bad health conditions, etc. Again, the coverage of sub-components is unbalanced: we chose eight indicators to represent the ‘achievement in basic skills’, while the measure of early school leaving (which is part of both the EU and other international initiatives, like OECD Doing Better for Children, IRC7, TÁRKI 2011) is shifted to the Youth module. The early school leaving indicator, in methodological terms, refers to the 18-24 age group and not to children, as defined in IPOLIS. On the one hand, in fact this measure provides information on the late childhood phase and any efficient policy action should be taken in this period or even earlier. On the other hand, the main risk which is attached to early school leaving, namely that young people will enter the labour market with inadequate skills, occurs among the youth. At national level there would be better measures available, based on school level administrative data. These data would allow for a continuous monitoring of the drop out process by grades.

- Taking into account the strong predictive power of achievement in skills for later outcomes, we propose to measure both the share of low achievers and the gap in outcomes between children with low and highly educated parents (using this variable as a proxy for social status). The educational system itself and specific policies should aim both at the same time: improving performance and reducing inequalities by family background. However, we faced some difficulty in keeping balance across components and sub-components when measures of achievement in basic skills were considered. In total, three basic skills are measured by the above mentioned comparative surveys: literacy in reading (PIRLS at the 4th grade, PISA at age 15), mathematics and science (TIMSS at the 4th grade, PISA at age 15). PIRLS and TIMSS have a time periodicity of 4 years in data collection, while PISA has a periodicity of 3 years. One difficulty comes from selecting between these skills. Although there are initiatives (e.g. OECD Doing Better for Children), which use a single measure composed by these three competencies (assuming one latent factor measured by three dimensions), we decided to include them separately. We consider that each of them plays an important and distinctive role in later cognitive outcomes. The other difficulty is related to the design of the PISA survey. The three-year periodicity becomes in fact a nine-year periodicity when one aims to go beyond the most basic indicators. The problem here is that the test has in focus another competency every three years, in a rotational way (2000, 2009 - reading; 2003, 2012 - mathematics; 2006 - science), while the two others are measured by a simplified test. Although the questionnaire of these simplified tests are designed to measure the given competency in a comparable way to the full test of the previous waves, the OECD do not publish otherwise regular statistics (like differences in mean test-scores according family background) on this basis. Our choice to include all three competencies at both age of 10 and 15 resulted in an asset of 9 indicators representing the ‘achievement in basic skills’ sub-component. At age 10 only the proportion of low achievers is considered by each competency and by parental education. Both the share of low achievers and the literacy gap of low social status pupils compared to those from a high social background are considered at age 15, for each of the three competencies.

Table 5 Summary table of indicators related to the domain ‘education and training’

Components and sub-components	EU	OTHER INTERNATIONAL	NATIONAL
Access to and quality of education			
Early childhood education	Share of children in early childhood education (SPC, ETM)	TÁRKI: participation in pre-primary education	US: Children ages 3–5 who were read to 3 or more times in the last week (AC) New Zealand: early childhood education participation rate (3, 4 year olds)
Educational attainment	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Lifelong learning	Not relevant for children		
Educational achievement			
Achievement in basic skills	Low reading literacy performance of pupils (aged 15) (OMC SIP) Low achievers in reading, maths, sciences (ETM)	OECD: average mean literacy score of pupils aged 15, literacy inequality among pupils aged 15 IRC 7: average achievement in reading, mathematical and science literacy (pupils aged 15) TÁRKI: low reading literacy performance of pupils aged 10 and 15	US: Mathematics and reading achievement (AC); Reading test scores: averages of ages 9, 13, and 17; Mathematics test scores: average of ages 9, 13, and 17) (CWI) Wales: Mathematics, reading and science scores (PISA) New Zealand: Mathematics, reading and science scores (PISA)
Early school leaving	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		

Abbreviations

AC – America’s Children: Key National Indicators of Well-Being
 CWI – Child and Youth Well-Being Index
 ETM – Education and Training Monitor 2013
 IRC 7 – UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (2007)
 OECD – OECD Doing Better for Children (2009)
 OMC – Portfolio of Indicators for the Monitoring of the European Strategy for Social Protection and Social Inclusion (2009)
 SIP – Social Inclusion Portfolio
 TÁRKI – TÁRKI (2011)
 New Zealand – Children and Young People
 Wales – Children and Young People’s Monitor

5.4 Health and risk behaviours

Indicators of health status, health behaviours and risk behaviours are included in all reviewed child indicator systems, albeit under somewhat different domains. In the OECD Doing Better for Children, UNICEF IRC 7 and in TÁRKI (2011), health behaviours (in the former two reports along with safety) and risk behaviours are separate dimensions, while in SPC (2012), health-related indicators are covered in the context of ‘access to quality services’. The ‘health and risk behaviours’ domain in IPOLIS is organised in three components: (i) health status, (ii) health behaviours, and (iii) risk behaviours (see Table 6).

5.4.1 Health status

The component ‘health status’ is divided into ‘objective’ and ‘subjective health status’ sub-components. In IPOLIS, like in other child indicator systems, the objective health status of children is in the spotlight.

5.4.1.1 Objective health

- Indicators used to measure the objective health status of children are all early childhood indicators (exceptions are to be found in national child reports, e.g. the indicator of long-standing illness). All the reports reviewed include indicators of low birth weight, infant mortality, and immunization rates. Additionally, the OECD Doing Better for Children and TÁRKI (2011) use breastfeeding rates, albeit, different ones: breastfeeding initiation rates and exclusive breastfeeding rates.

- To measure the objective health status of children in IPOLIS two indicators will be used: the proportion of children with low birth weight (less than 2,500 grams/5 lbs 8oz) and infant mortality rate (per 1,000 live births), both based on administrative data sources.
- Mental health status in the child reports appears to be a neglected issue relative to physical health status. In this respect IPOLIS is not different; all health related indicators of IPOLIS measure physical health (except one indicator of risk behaviours – see later).

5.4.1.2 Subjective health

- There are several reasons for using subjective indicators of health status. First, a description of young people’s health should include their perspectives of their emotional and physical well-being. Second, indicators of subjective health are more relevant than indicators of morbidity and mortality for the whole population of young people, for the simple reason that they include all of them, not just subgroups. Third, in terms of impact, subjective indicators have objective behavioural consequences (e.g. perceived health problems can motivate young people to stay away from school, etc.) (Currie et al 2004: 55). Yet, despite that internationally comparable data on young people’s subjective health status are available from HBSC surveys, cross-national child reports has given relatively little attention to subjective indicators of health status.
- HBSC surveys use three indicators of subjective health status: self-rated health (proportion of young people rating their health as fair or poor), subjective health complaints (based on a standard symptom checklist), and life satisfaction.
- Subjective assessment of health is covered in the IRC 7 (albeit under the domain ‘subjective wellbeing’), TÁRKI (2011) and in national level child wellbeing indicator systems (e.g. the Child and Youth Well-Being Index and the Children and Young People's Monitor). The IRC 7 and the national reports draw on the question on self-rated health: Would you say that your health is Excellent, Good, Fair or Poor? They differ; however, in that perceived health status is formulated as negative indicator in IRC 7, while as positive in the national level indicator systems (see Table 6). In TÁRKI (2011), subjective health status of young people is measured by the indicator of life satisfaction. This reflects young people’s global evaluation of their lives. However, HBSC research has demonstrated that it is family and peer relationships that are the most important correlates of life satisfaction) (Currie et al 2004: 56). Since, as can be seen, the indicator of life satisfaction is not a pure measure of health status, we prefer to use the indicator of self-reported health. Despite the increasing use of positive indicators (especially in the U.S. but also outside), the negative wording is preferred here, since in it is still more prevalent in the EU (i.e. “percentage of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who rate their health as ‘fair or poor’).
- According to research findings, gender inequality in health increases significantly from the age of 11 to the age of 15, with an increasing risk of poor subjective health in girls. 15-year-old girls report a much less favourable pattern both in terms of poor health, health complaints and life satisfaction (Currie et al 2004: 61.). Based on these findings, beyond the breakdowns by age and family affluence scale (FAS)¹⁰, IPOLIS will use breakdowns by age and sex (see Table 10).

5.4.2 Health behaviours

- The only cross-national data source on health behaviours of children is the HBSC survey. Since HBSC collects data from children between the ages of 11 and 15, there are no cross-national data sources on the health behaviours of children under this age (Richardson 2012: 18).
- In general, the international child wellbeing indicator systems include numerous measures of health behaviours. They, however, differ in scope; while the OECD Doing Better for Children report and

¹⁰ FAS is a measure of family wealth, used by HBSC. It is computed from four individual indicators: number of cars, having a bedroom and number of holidays and number of computers. For more details, see Currie et al. (2004).

the SPC (2012) single out one indicator (physical activity and obesity, respectively), UNICEF IRC 7 and TÁRKI (2011) embrace a wider range of health behaviours, such as eating habits, oral hygiene, or obesity. In what follows, we focus on only two aspects of health behaviours: physical activity and obesity.

5.4.2.1 Physical activity

- Physical activity is a commonly used indicator of health behaviours. Data on physical activity are available from HBSC for all age cohorts (11, 13 and 15 year-olds). The 2001/2002 HBSC survey revised the previous questions on physical activity and introduced a new measure of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity carried out at school and/or in free time. The present questionnaire contains two questions: the first question is about physical activity of at least moderate intensity undertaken in the previous week, and the second about a typical week. The response options for both questions range from 0 day to 7 days. Scores are calculated by averaging the results for the two items. A score of 5 or more classifies the student as meeting the recommended physical activity a day on most days. HBSC reports on both the mean number of days when young people undertake moderate-to-vigorous physical activity for at least an hour (average of the previous week and a typical week) and the percentage of young people who undertake at least one hour of moderate-to-vigorous activity a day on most days.
- Of the reviewed child wellbeing reports, IRC 7 uses the former measure of physical activity, while the OECD Doing Better for Children prefers the latter. IPOLIS will include the percentage of students who undertake more than one hour of at least moderate activity a day on most days (5 or more a week), since research shows that it provides a reasonable estimate of those meeting the current guidelines on physical activity (Currie et al. 2011).
- HBSC research has demonstrated that the levels of physical activity decline with age, particularly among girls (Currie et al. 2004: 90). However, the relationship between age and physical activity levels varies across countries. Cross-country differences can be explained by several factors, e.g. national differences in the role of physical education at school, free time available during the school day for non-organized activities (ibid). Based on the research findings, in case of this indicator, we apply the following breakdowns: (i) age, (ii) age and sex, and (iii) FAS.

5.4.2.2 Obesity

- Childhood obesity is a serious public health problem. As the EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity 2014-2020 states, “The rise in overweight and obesity in children and young people is distressing given the strong link between excess adiposity and detrimental health and psychosocial outcomes in later life. These include, but are not limited to, cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, certain cancers and musculoskeletal disorders, as well as social stigmatization and mental health problems. Research shows that, compared to normal weight children, those who are overweight or obese are more likely to go on to become obese adults, and so are at an increased risk of suffering from associated health problems”¹¹. For children and young people, a healthy diet and a physically active lifestyle can reduce the risk of overweight and obesity in adulthood as well as contributing to healthy growth and development¹².
- In case of children, the only source of information of this type is the HBSC survey. It collects data on children’s eating habits, body weight and size, and dieting and other weight control behaviours. Data on weight and height are used for body mass index (BMI) calculations¹³.
- Self-reported data on weight and height, however, raise some problems. First, a very high proportion (over 25%) of individual BMI data is missing in a couple of countries. An analysis suggests

¹¹ http://ec.europa.eu/health/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/childhoodobesity_actionplan_2014_2020_en.pdf.

¹² http://ec.europa.eu/health/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/childhoodobesity_actionplan_2014_2020_en.pdf.

¹³ HBSC uses age- and sex-specific BMI international cut-off points to calculate the prevalence of overweight (see Currie et al. 2011: 134).

that there is a clear bias in the non-reporting of these data. According to findings, non-responding young people are more likely to be overweight or obese, and dissatisfied with the size and weight of their bodies (Currie et al. 2004: 127). Second, reliability of self-reported height and weight data is also questionable. An analysis from U.S. suggests that the rates for overweight and obesity derived through self-reporting measures are quite accurate (Strauss 1999; Currie et al. 2004). Other investigators, however, came to the conclusion that self-reported obesity measures should be treated with caution (see e.g. Tienboon et al. 1992).

- HBSC reports on the percentages of obese and pre-obese 13 and 15 year-olds. Information on the 11-year-olds is not presented due to the high proportion of missing data (many of them may not know their height and weight). The term overweight as used by HBSC covers both the obese and the pre-obese.
- The issue of overweight and obesity is covered in IRC 7 and in SPC (albeit in the latter for young people aged 18-24). IRC 7 presents the percentage of young people age 13 and 15 who report being overweight.
- Despite the bias in non-reporting of weight and height data, IPOLIS will include a measure of overweight because of the importance of the issue. Since evidence suggests that countries with higher percentages of pre-obesity also report a higher prevalence of obesity (see Currie et al. 2011: 139), it is reasonable to use a combined measure of overweight (including both the pre-obese and obese).
- However, it is necessary to pay close attention to the non-reporting rates that vary greatly from country to country. According to the 2011 HBSC report, the proportion of missing BMI data is particularly high in some countries: Belgium (French), England, Greenland, Ireland, Lithuania, Malta and Scotland. With the exception of Belgium, Ireland and Lithuania, these countries also have a higher prevalence of overweight (and obesity).
- Research findings show that socioeconomic background strongly influences the development of overweight in adolescents (Drewnowski et al. 1994 in Currie et al. 2011: 141). It is, therefore important, to apply breakdowns not only by socio-demographic variables (age and sex), but also by socio-economic status (FAS).

5.4.3 Risk behaviours

IPOLIS covers a broader set of indicators related to risk behaviours than do the cross-national child wellbeing indicator systems reviewed here. The component 'risk behaviours' in IPOLIS includes 6 sub-components: (i) smoking, (ii) alcohol consumption, (iii) illicit drug use, (iv) teenage births, (v) psychological distress, and (vi) suicide. Two of these, teenage births and psychological distress, are discussed in the Youth module of IPOLIS.

5.4.3.1 Substance use

- Data on substance use are collected in ESPAD and HBSC. Although ESPAD covers substance use in more detail than HBSC, the latter has the advantage of collecting information on younger children too. While ESPAD asks 16-year-old students, HBSC asks students in three age groups: 11, 13, and 15 year-olds. In practice, however, due to the low prevalence of substance use among 11-year-olds, data are either presented only for the older age groups. For example, HBSC reports on drug use only for the 15-year-olds.
- Smoking and alcohol consumption are covered in all child wellbeing reports reviewed, while illicit drug/cannabis use is not reported on by OECD Doing Better for Children (see Table 6).

5.4.3.2 Smoking

- Tobacco smoking is identified by WHO as the leading cause of premature illness and death in developed countries (Murray and Lopez 1996 in Currie et al. 2011: 76). Although the vast majority

of smoking-related deaths occur in middle-aged and elderly people, smoking behaviour is established in adolescence. Further, smoking is associated with adverse short-term health effects in young people (e.g. reduced lung function, increased asthmatic problems, etc.). Smoking is also a major concern, for it is considered as the first step on a path that might lead to other forms of substance use (Currie et al. 2011: 79-82).

- Relatively few questions are asked about smoking in both ESPAD and HBSC. ESPAD asks children about access and regularity of tobacco smoking, including lifetime and past-30-days prevalence of smoking. HBSC collects data on tobacco initiation and regularity of smoking at the moment (with response options of “I do not smoke”, “less than once a week”, “at least once a week but not every day”, “every day”).
- Smoking is covered in all child wellbeing reports and in SPC too. The proportion of regular smokers, the most commonly used indicator of smoking, is defined either as those who smoke at least once a week or those who smoked daily. In OECD Doing Better for Children and UNICEF IRC 7, the percentage of 15 year-olds who smoke at least once a week (based on HBSC data on smoking at the moment), while in TÁRKI (2011) and SPC (2012) the proportion of daily smokers is used as a measure of regular smoking (in TÁRKI: in the 16-year-old population, based on ESPAD data on past-30-days prevalence of smoking; and in SPC: in the population aged 15-24, based on EHIS data).
- IPOLIS will include the percentage of 15 year-olds who smoke every day as the indicator of regular smoking. A strong argument for this is that it makes data on children and young people comparable. (Data on smoking behaviours among young people is available from EHIS, and the relevant question refers to daily or occasional smoking.)

5.4.3.3 Alcohol consumption

- A range of questions are asked about alcohol use in ESPAD. Items cover access to alcohol, age of first use, regularity of drinking, type and volume of beverages used on the last occasion, prevalence of heavy episodic drinking, and consequences of alcohol consumption. HBSC asks children about age at first use, regularity of drinking and drunkenness.
- Of the measures of alcohol consumption it is excessive use that seems to be preferred over regular use by the child wellbeing reports reviewed. Both OECD Doing Better for Children and UNICEF IRC 7 report on the percentage of those who have been drunk at least twice. It is to be noted, however, that the indicator of drunkenness, raises the problem of subjectivity. Drunkenness might mean quite different things for children living in different drinking cultures (TÁRKI 2011). An alternative measure of excessive use is heavy episodic drinking (often referred to as binge drinking¹⁴). ESPAD asks students how many times during the past 30 days they had five drinks or more on one occasion. Heavy episodic drinking – defined as the consumption of five alcoholic drinks or more on one occasion – would cause most adolescents to reach at least some degree of intoxication (Hibell et al. 2012: 77). This measure is used by the 2011 TÁRKI report as well as the America's Children and the Child and Youth Well-Being Index. Since heavy episodic drinking is a more objective measure of alcohol misuse than drunkenness, we prefer to use this one in IPOLIS.
- However, because of the existence of different drinking cultures – which are characterized by different combinations of regularity of drinking and extent of drunkenness –, no single best instrument exists for measuring alcohol consumption (Currie et al. 2004). Therefore, in order to get an overall picture, a measure of regular drinking should also be included in IPOLIS. Both ESPAD and HBSC ask questions about the regularity of drinking by the type of alcoholic beverage. For our purpose here, the question asked in HBSC seems to be easier to handle. Based on this, IPOLIS will include the proportion of 15-year-olds who drink anything alcoholic (including beer,

¹⁴ In the 2011 report, ESPAD quits using the term „binge drinking” which was used in the previous three reports because „binge” refers to the time frame of drinking, and no time frame is specific in the ESPAD questionnaire (Hibell et al. 2012: 77).

wine, spirits/liquors, alcopops, cider or any other drink that contains alcohol) at least once a week as a measure of regular alcohol consumption.

5.4.3.4 Illicit drug use

- Drug taking is covered in more detail in ESPAD than in HBSC. While the latter survey includes cannabis use only, ESPAD also asks young people about experiences of using a range of other illicit drugs like tranquillizers or sedatives, amphetamines, LSD or some other hallucinogens, crack, cocaine, relevin, heroin, “magic mushrooms”, GHB, anabolic steroids, drugs by injection with a needle (like heroin, cocaine, amphetamine), alcohol with pills (medicaments) in order to get high.
- It is known that the most prevalent illicit drug in all ESPAD countries is cannabis. IRC 7 reports on past-12-months prevalence of cannabis use only, while the 2011 TÁRKI report and the indicator systems developed in the U.S. cover illicit drugs. TÁRKI (2011) includes lifetime prevalence of any illicit drug use (including cannabis) and lifetime prevalence of non-prescription use of tranquillizers/sedatives. As it seems, no consensus on a single indicator of drug use has been reached.
- An analysis of the 2011 ESPAD data shows that the vast majority of students, who have tried any illicit drug, have used marijuana or hashish (cannabis) (Hibell et al. 2012: 85). That is the proportion of those reporting experience with cannabis is close to the total prevalence of illicit drugs in general. The correlation between the two variables is almost perfect ($r=0.99$), meaning that countries scoring high on illicit drugs are also very likely to score high on cannabis, and vice versa (Hibell et al. 2012: 85). Considering these findings, and also that new drugs are emerging at an unprecedented rate, it seems more reasonable to measure lifetime use of any illicit drug (including cannabis) rather than that of cannabis alone. Thus IPOLIS includes the indicator of lifetime use of illicit drugs (the percentage of young people who have ever used any of the illicit drugs listed in the ESPAD questionnaire).

5.4.3.5 Suicide

- Suicide is one of the three leading causes of death among young people worldwide (EC 2000). The suicide death rate is defined as the crude death rate from suicide and intentional self-harm per 100 000 people. Eurostat disseminates data for young people aged 15 to 19. (The WHO Mortality databases use the following age groups: 1-4, 5-14, 15-24).
- Youth suicide rates are often used as an indicator of mental health (albeit an extreme one); see for example OECD Doing Better for Children, and the national child wellbeing indicators systems.
- The reliability of suicide statistics, however, is often questioned. Suicides are underreported for cultural and religious reasons, as well as owing to different classification and ascertainment procedures. Suicide can be masked by other diagnostic categories of causes of death. Unfortunately, in cases of young people, death due to suicide is often misclassified or masked by other mortality diagnoses (Wasserman et al. 2005).
- However, self-harm thoughts and suicide attempts are documented precursors of completed suicide. It is therefore important to investigate the prevalence of suicide thoughts and attempts (Kokkevi et al. 2012).
- Data on self-harm ideation and suicide attempts are available from ESPAD. Students are asked “Has any of the following ever happened to you?” The item list includes: “thought of harming yourself” and “attempted suicide”. Responses range from “not at all” to “5 or more times”.¹⁵
- To measure this type of risk behaviour IPOLIS includes on the one hand, the suicide rates for young people aged 15 to 19 (in the Youth module) and on the other, the self-reported measure of suicide attempts in young people aged 16.

¹⁵ ESPAD data on self-harm thoughts and suicide attempts are not disseminated on a regular basis. The 2007 ESPAD report includes a special “Psychosocial module” reporting on young people’s suicidal thoughts and behaviours.

Table 6 Summary table of indicators related to the domain 'health and risk behaviours'

Components and sub-components	EU	OTHER INTERNATIONAL	NATIONAL
Health status			
Objective health status	Low birth weight (OMC HP)(SPC); Infant mortality rate (OMC HP)(SPC)	OECD: Low birth weight (<2500g); Infant mortality rate; Vaccination rates for pertussis and for measles by the age of 2; Breastfeeding initiation rates; Child mortality rates for all causes. IRC 7: Low birth weight (<2500g); Infant mortality rate; Percentage of children age 12-23 months immunized against measles, polio, and DPT3). TÁRKI: Low birth weight; Infant mortality; Vaccination; Exclusive breastfeeding at 3,4,6 month	US: Preterm birth (AC); Low birth-weight (AC, CWI); Infant mortality rate (AC, CWI); Immunization rate (AC); Rate of children with activity limitations due to health problems (CWI 0-18; AC: 5-17) Wales: Low birth weight; Infant mortality rate; Immunization rate; Breastfeeding; Percentage of children who report having a long-standing illness/limiting long-standing illness (Welsh Health Survey: 15y) New Zealand: Low birth weight; Infant mortality rate; Immunization rate
Subjective health status	-	IRC7: Percentage of young people rating their own health as 'fair or poor' (HBSC: 11,13,15) TÁRKI: General satisfaction with life (HBSC:15 y)	US: Rate of children with very good or excellent health (CWI: 0-18) Wales: Percentage reporting their health to be good or excellent (Welsh Health Survey 8-15,16-24; HBSC 11-15)
Health behaviours			
Physical activity	-	OECD: Percentage of children doing moderate-to-vigorous physical activity daily (HBSC) IRC7: Percentage aged 11,13,15, who report at least one hour of moderate vigorous activity daily (HBSC) TÁRKI: Physical activity (HBSC: 13y)	Wales: Percentage of young people who report at least one hour of moderate to vigorous activity daily(HBSC) New Zealand: Proportion of young people aged 15–24 years who meet physical activity guidelines
Obesity	Young people (18-24) with a BMI of 30 or above (SPC: context indicator)	IRC7: Percentage aged 11,13,15 who are overweight according to BMI (HBSC)	US: Percentage of children who are obese (CWI: 6-19; AC:2-19) Wales: Percentage of 11 to 15-years-old overweight or obese (HBSC) New Zealand: Proportion of children aged 5–14 years who are obese
Risk behaviours			
Smoking	Regular smokers (15-24) (SPC: context indicator)	OECD: Percentage of 15 year-old children who smoke at least once a week* IRC 7: Percentage of 11,13,15 year-olds who smoke at least once a week (HBSC) TÁRKI: Proportion of daily smokers (ESPAD: 16y)	US: Percentage of students who reported smoking cigarettes in the last 30 days (CWI: Grade 12); Percentage of students who reported smoking cigarettes daily in the past 30 days AC: Grades 8, 10, 12) Wales: Percentage of students who reported weekly smoking (HBSC:15y) New Zealand: proportion of students who smoke cigarettes regularly (14-15y)
Alcohol consumption	-	OECD: Percentage of 13,15 year-old children who have been drunk at least twice IRC 7: Percentage of 11,13,15 year-olds who have been drunk two or more times (HBSC) TÁRKI: Alcohol use in the last 30 days (ESPAD:16y); Drinking 6 or more times in the last 30 days (ESPAD:16y); Binge drinking in the last 30 days (ESPAD:16y); Having been drunk in the last 30 days (ESPAD:16y)	US: Percentage of students who reported binge drinking in the last 30 days (CWI: grade 12); Percentage of students who reported binge drinking in the past 2 weeks (AC: grades 8,10,12) Wales: Percentage drinking alcohol weekly (HBSC:15 years); Drunkenness on four occasions or more (HBSC)

Illicit drugs	-	IRC 7: Percentage of 11, 13, 15 year-olds who report having used cannabis in the last 12 months (HBSC). TÁRKI: Lifetime prevalence rate for any illicit drug use (ESPAD:16y)	US: Percentage of students who reported using any illicit drugs in the last 30 days (CWI: Grade 12; AC: Grades 8,10,12) Wales: Percentage of 15-years-old reporting cannabis use (HBSC)
Teenage births	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Psychological distress	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		
Suicide	Death caused by suicide (15-24) (SPC: context indicator)	OECD (2009): Youth suicide rate (15-19)	US: Suicide rate (CWI: 10-19; AC: grades 9 through 12) Wales: Suicide rates (15-24); New Zealand: Youth suicide rate (15-24)

Abbreviations

AC – America's Children: Key National Indicators of Well-Being

CWI – Child and Youth Well-Being Index

HP – Health Portfolio

IRC 7 – UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (2007)

OECD – OECD Doing Better for Children (2009)

OMC – Portfolio of Indicators for the Monitoring of the European Strategy for Social Protection and Social Inclusion (2009)

SPC – SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (2012)

TÁRKI – TÁRKI (2011)

New Zealand – Children and Young People

Wales – Children and Young People's Monitor

5.5 Social connectedness and civic participation

The formation of close attachments to family, peers, and community has been linked to healthy youth development in numerous studies¹⁶. Yet, we currently lack regular indicators on relationships with parents and peers, and civic involvement. Of the international child wellbeing reports family relationships are covered only in IRC 7, peer relationships in IRC 7 and OECD Doing Better for Children initiative, while civic participation is not included in any of them. The SPC (2102), however, highlights the importance of measuring children's participation in social, recreational, sporting and cultural activities, since it enhances self-confidence as well as social and civic skills, and thus is crucial to the promotion of a child's overall development (SPC 2012: 38).

The 'social connectedness and civic participation' domain of IPOLIS contains two components: (i) family and peer relationships, and (ii) civic participation.

5.5.1 Family and peer relationships

5.5.1.1 Family relationships

- Three child surveys collect data on children's relationships with their parents: PISA, HBSC and ESPAD. In the 2000 wave of PISA, children were asked about how often their parents spent time talking to them and how often parents ate their main meal at home with them. HBSC surveys ask children about the quality of parental communication: How easy is it for you to talk to the following persons about things that really bother you? Father/Mother. The ESPAD questionnaire contains a number of items related to family relationships. Young people are asked about how they are satisfied with the relationships with their mothers and fathers as well as about parental care and control.
- Of the reviewed child well-being reports it is only IRC 7 in which family relationships are covered. The IRC 7 report uses the questions about "parental time" from PISA as indicators of family relationships. Since these questions have not been repeated since, we need to find other measures for IPOLIS. To measure family relationships we include the percentage of young people who find it easy to communicate with their mothers/fathers.

16 <http://www.childstats.gov/americaschildren/famsoc8.asp>.

5.5.1.2 Peer relationships

- Relationships with peers assume greater importance as children grow up. As the World Health Organization points out being liked and accepted by peers is important in the health and development of young people (Currie et al. 2004: 34). Peer relationships, however, are difficult to define and measure. Few attempts have been made to include measures of peer relationships in the child wellbeing indicator systems. It can be added that there have been even fewer attempts to capture the positive side of peer relationships. As can be seen from Table 7, it is only the Children and Young People's Monitor of Wales that include indicators of peer relationships other than bullying (which is discussed under a separate section below).
- A key source of data on peer relationships (other than those discussed under the component 'risk behaviours') is the HBSC survey. Three indicators are used to measure peer influence in HBSC: the size of the friendship group, the frequency of peer contact, communication with friends through electronic media. The size of the friendship group (number of close friends) is a measure that appears to be culturally influenced. An obvious explanation is a difference in the semantic meaning of "close friends". It is notable that groups of countries with similar language types have similar frequencies (Currie et al. 2004: 35). Frequency of contact is measured by two questions on meeting with friends in the afternoon (right after school) and in the evening. The amount of time spent with friends could be a strong predictor for the influence of peers on the individual. However, differences in the school systems have a strong effect on the cross-country differences (the probability of meeting friends is lower where the school hours are extended to the afternoon). The third measure of peer relationships is peer contact through electronic media (EMC). Young people are asked how often they talk to friends on the phone, send them text messages, or have contact through the internet. HBSC reports on the proportions who reported EMC with their friends every day. EMC communication with friends has been associated with potential benefits and risks (such as cyberbullying, engagement with risk behaviours). However, recent evidence suggests that greater use of EMC is associated with more face-to-face contacts with friends (Currie et al. 2012: 37).
- In the HBSC survey, there are three additional items designed to measure peer support: proportion agreeing or strongly agreeing that classmates enjoy being together; proportion agreeing or strongly agreeing that they are accepted by peers; and proportion agreeing or strongly agreeing that classmates are kind and helpful. According to a HBSC report, these three measures are highly similar across all countries and regions (Currie et al. 2004: 43.). In the IRC 7 report, the percentage of those agreeing or strongly agreeing that classmates are kind and helpful is used as indicator of peer relationships. This measure is associated with positive effects only, and being so it is easy to be interpreted. (It is to be noted that ESPAD also collects data on peer support. Young people are asked a question about how often happens that they get emotional support from their best friends.)
- In IPOLIS, the percentage of young people who find their peers kind and helpful is to serve as a measure of peer relationships.

5.5.1.3 Bullying victimization

- As it was mentioned earlier, bullying (and fighting) was a sub-component of the component 'risk behaviours' in the first version of IPOLIS presented in the ICP. In a later stage, however, it seemed more appropriate to measure "the other side of the coin", namely: being the victim of bullying or bullying victimization. Therefore, bullying victimization has been relocated in the domain 'family and peer relationships'.
- Data on children's school relationships are abundant: four surveys collect data on this: HBSC, ESPAD, TIMSS and PIRLS. The questions in the HBSC survey address the frequency of being the victim of bullying and bullying others. Children are asked the following questions: How often have you been bullied at school in the past couple of months? (victimisation); How often have you taken part in bullying another student(s) at school in the past couple of months? The response options for both are the same: "I haven't been bullied/bullied another student(s)", "It has only happened

once or twice”, “2 or 3 times a month”, “About once a week”, “Several times a week”. Question about being bullied and bullying others are also asked in PIRLS and ESPAD, though, in a slightly different manner.

- The child wellbeing reports covering this issue use HBSC data. IRC 7 reports on the percentage of students who were bullied at least once, while OECD Doing Better for Children on those who were bullied at least twice in the previous two months. The latter is a measure of repeated victimization, indicative of young people of higher risk.
- An analysis of HBSC data suggest that prevalence rates of being bullied (at both levels of frequency) decline with age in most countries (Currie et al. 2011). Victimization shows relatively little gender differences overall and in most countries. Bullying rates differ considerably across countries. (Currie et al. 2004: 147; Currie et al. 2011: 200).
- Bullying victimization is measured in IPOLIS by the proportion of those who report being bullied at least once during the previous couple of months.¹⁷ It is important to point out, however, that bullying is difficult to define in some languages, and accordingly country variations should be interpreted with caution (Currie et al. 2011: 147).

5.5.2 Civic participation

- Civic participation in IPOLIS is not confined to the sphere of politics but include both political and non-political participation. Indeed, in case of children it is the latter which is more relevant. Non-political participation includes participation in the activity of different organizations or groups such as youth groups or environmental organizations, and volunteering.
- We know very little about the civic participation of children in the EU as a whole. This is mainly explained by the lack of systematic and comparable data. Social participation questions are asked in only ICCS, directly of children (and in the preceding CIVED). The ICCS measures civic participation (outside of school) by asking students aged 13 to 14 years to state whether they participated either within the last 12 months or before in the activity of the following organizations: youth organizations affiliated with a political party or union, environmental organizations, human rights organizations, voluntary groups doing something to help the community, organizations collecting money for a social cause, cultural organizations based on ethnicity, and groups or young people campaigning for an issue.
- Of the above list, involvement in groups helping the community and undertaking charity collections are the most frequent forms of participation among lower-secondary school students across ICCS countries (Schultz et al. 2010).
- The ICP recommended that group membership and volunteering be measured separately. Unfortunately, the lack of data does not allow us to include one indicator for each type of civic participation. Therefore, we propose to measure civic participation by the “percentage of students who have ever participated in at least one of the listed civic activities (either within the last 12 months or prior to that)”.

¹⁷ In the ICP, the proposed structure of IPOLIS includes “bullying” as a component of the domain ‘health and risk behaviours’. However, after having selected the indicator “bullying victimization”, it seemed reasonable to regroup it into the domain ‘family and peer relationships’.

Table 7 Summary table of indicators related to the domain 'social connectedness and participation'

Components and sub-components	EU	OTHER INTERNATIONAL	NATIONAL
Family and peer relationships			
Family relationships	-	IRC 7: Percentage of 15-year olds who report eating the main meal with parents more than once a week; Percentage of 15-year olds who report that parents spend time 'just talking to them' several times per week (PISA);	US: Rate of substantiated maltreatment reports of children aged (AC: 0-17) New Zealand: Share of children who reported on positive relationship with parents (12-18) Wales: Percentage of children who report finding it easy to talk to father/mother (HBSC:11-15)
Peer relationships	-	IRC 7: Percentage of young people age 11,13,15 who report being bullied in the previous 2 months; Percentage of young people age 11,13,15 involved in fighting in last 12 months (HBSC) OECD: Percentage of 11,13,15-year-old children bullied at school at least twice in the past two months	New Zealand: Proportion of students who reported being bullied at school (12-18) Wales: Percentage of children who report finding it easy to talk to best friend (HBSC:11-15); Percentage of young people who report finding their peers kind and helpful (HBSC 15y); Percentage of young people who spend four or more evenings per week with their friends (HBSC:11-15); Percentage of young people who use EMC on five or more days per week (HBSC:11-15); Percentage of young people who were bullied 2-3 times a month (HBSC: 11-15)
Civic participation			
Voting/Voter turnout	Not relevant for children		
Group membership/Volunteering	-	-	Wales: Percentage of respondents who volunteered for an organization, friends, neighbours or other members of the community in the last 12 months (National Survey for Wales Pilot: 16-25)
Internet use	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module		

Abbreviations

AC – America's Children: Key National Indicators of Well-Being
 IRC 7 – UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (2007)
 OECD – OECD Doing Better for Children (2009)
 New Zealand – Children and Young People
 Wales – Children and Young People's Monitor

5.6 Environmental quality and physical safety

5.6.1 Environmental quality

The environment children live in plays an important role in their health and development. Children may be more vulnerable than adults to the adverse effects of environmental contaminants in air, drinking water, and other sources because their bodies are still developing. Yet international child well-being reports do not devote much space to the quality of environment children live in.

- Unfortunately, there are no EU data on levels of environmental pollution for children in the home (e.g. environmental tobacco smoke). Data on children's exposure to environmental pollution outside the home are sparse too.
- The key sources of information on local environments are EU-SILC and EQLS. EU-SILC asks whether the household's accommodation has "any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry". A separate question is asked in EU-SILC about noise from neighbours or from the street (of traffic, business, factories, etc.). The questionnaire of EQLS includes a series of possible complaints about the immediate neighbourhood in terms of noise, air pollution, quality of drinking water, crime, violence or vandalism, litter or rubbish on the street,

and traffic congestion. Also, there is a question about the access to recreational or green areas. Beyond EU-SILC and EQLS, HBSC also asks children some questions about the characteristics of the locality, like litter, broken glass or rubbish lying around or run-down house or building in the area.

- Of the cross-national child wellbeing reports it is only OECD Doing Better for Children that includes a measure of environmental quality: the percentage of children living in homes with poor environmental conditions. Poor environmental condition is defined in a broad sense as either having noise or any pollution/grime/other environmental problem.
- To measure the presence of environmental problems in the immediate neighbourhood the same EU-SILC questions will be used in IPOLIS, as in OECD Doing Better for Children, but not in a combined manner. IPOLIS will include two indicators: one for measuring the percentage of children living in households that reported noise from neighbours or from the street, and one for measuring the percentage of children living in households that reported any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry. (Unfortunately, the existing data infrastructure does not allow to measure air pollution problems separately from other environmental problems.)

5.6.2 Physical safety

In addition to causing direct physical harm to young victims, serious violence can adversely affect their mental health and development.

- Questions about crime are asked in EU-SILC, ESS and in HBSC. EU-SILC asks about whether respondents (the household reference persons) have experiences of violent crime in the area. ESS asks respondents about whether they (or their household members) have been victim of burglary in the last 5 years and whether they feel safe walking in their area. HBSC also covers the subjective perception of safety in the neighbourhood by asking children whether they feel safe in the area they live. (Answer options include “always”, “most of the time”, “sometimes”, “rarely or never”).
- Cross-country child reports rarely attempt to measure the physical safety of children in the area where they live. One exception is IRC 7 which includes an overall measure of safety: deaths from accidents and injuries per 100 000 under 19 years. This measure covers deaths caused by accidents, murder, suicide and violence.
- IPOLIS will include two measures: the percentage of children who live in households that report experiences of violent crime in the area; and the percentage of young people aged 11, 13, and 15 who report not always feeling safe in the area where they live. The former measure is extracted from EU-SILC, while the latter one is based on child reported data from HBSC.

Table 8 Summary table of indicators related to the domain 'environmental quality and physical safety'

Components and sub-components	EU	OTHER INTERNATIONAL	NATIONAL
<i>Environmental quality</i>	-	OECD (2009): Percentage of children living in homes with poor environmental conditions* (EU-SILC: 0-17)	US: Percentage of children living in counties with pollutant concentrations above the levels of the current air quality standards (AC: 0-17)
<i>Physical safety</i>	-	IRC 7: Deaths from accidents and injuries under 19 years**	US: Rate of violent crime victimization(AC: 12-17; CWI:12-19); Injury deaths of children (1-4; 5-14) and adolescents (15-19) (AC) Wales: Percentage of children stated they were victims of crime (British Crime Survey: 10-15); Child casualties by type of road use (0-15); Percentage of medically attended injuries in the last 12 months (HBSC: 11-15) New Zealand: Unintentional injury mortality rate (0-14); Assault mortality rate (0-14, 15-24); Criminal victimization (New Zealand Crime and Safety Survey: 15-24); Proportion of young people aged 15-24 who said that fear of crime had a moderate or high impact on their quality of life (New Zealand Crime and Safety Survey); Road traffic injury and death rate (0-14, 15-24)

Notes. *noise from neighbours or outside/any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic and industry.

**Accidents, murder, suicide, and violence

Abbreviations

AC – America's Children: Key National Indicators of Well-Being

CWI – Child and Youth Well-Being Index

IRC 7 – UNICEF Innocenti Report Card 7 (2007)

OECD – OECD Doing Better for Children (2009)

New Zealand – Children and Young People

Wales – Children and Young People's Monitor

Table 9 Overview of the IPOLIS Child module indicators

	Name	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Overarching
1. MATERIAL LIVING CONDITIONS					
1.1 Poverty					
<i>Extent</i>	At-risk-of-poverty rate after social transfers	The share of children (aged 0 to 17) with an equivalised disposable income below the risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income (after social transfers) (%).	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. work intensity status	EU-SILC	Yes
	At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fix moment in time (2005)	Percentage of children who are at-risk-of-poverty referring to an at-risk-of-poverty threshold calculated in the standard way for the base year (60% of the 2005 national median equivalised disposable income) and adjusted for inflation only up to the income year considered. Adjustment is based on the annual harmonised index of consumer prices (HICP) of the income reference period.	-	EU-SILC	Yes
<i>Depth</i>	Relative median poverty gap	Difference between the median equivalised income of persons aged 0-17 below the at-risk-of poverty threshold and the threshold itself, expressed as a percentage of the at-risk-of poverty threshold (%).	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. work intensity status	EU-SILC	No
<i>Persistence</i>	Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate	The proportion of people (0-17) with an equivalised disposable income below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold in the current year and in at least 2 of the preceding 3 years (%).	a. highest education of parents	EU-SILC	Yes
1.2 Material deprivation					
	Severe material deprivation rate of children	Proportion of children living in a household in which at least four items are missing out of the nine below-mentioned items (%): 1. their rent, mortgage or utility bills; 2. keeping their home adequately warm; 3. facing unexpected expenses; 4. eating meat or proteins regularly; 5. going on holiday; 6. having a television set (enforced lack); 7. having a washing machine (enforced lack); 8. having a car (enforced lack); 9. having a telephone (enforced lack). The indicator distinguishes between individuals who cannot afford a certain good or service (enforced inability), and those who do not have this good or service for another reason, e.g. because they do not want or do not need it.	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC	Yes
	Inability to make ends meet	Proportion of children living in a household with the ability of making ends meet with difficulty or great difficulty (%).	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC	No

	Severe material deprivation rate of children – newly proposed to replace the currently used rate	Proportion of children living in households that cannot afford at least 6 out of the below-mentioned 18 items (%). The household cannot afford at least one child to have (enforced lack): 1. Some new (not second-hand) clothes; 2. Two pairs of properly fitting shoes, including a pair of all-weather shoes; 3. Fresh fruits & vegetables daily; 4. One meal with meat, chicken, fish or vegetarian equivalent daily; 5. Books at home suitable for the children’s age; 6. Outdoor leisure equipment; 7. Indoor games; 8. A suitable place to do homework; 9. Regular leisure activities (sports, youth organisations, etc.); 10. Celebrations on special occasions; 11. To invite friends round to play and eat from time to time; 12. To participate in school trips and school events that costs money; 13. One week annual holiday away from home. The household cannot afford: 14. To replace worn-out furniture; 15. To avoid arrears (mortgage or rent, utility bills or hire purchase instalments); 16. A computer and an Internet connection (enforced lack); 17. To keep home adequately warm (enforced lack); 18. A car/van for private use (enforced lack).	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC 2009 module	No
	Educational deprivation	Share of 15-year-old children reporting less than five educational items (out of seven: desk to study, a quiet place to work, a computer for schoolwork, educational software, an internet connection, a calculator, a dictionary, school textbook) among 15-year-olds in the school population.	a. ESCS	PISA	No
1.3 Housing					
<i>Overcrowding</i>	Overcrowding rate	Percentage of children living in an overcrowded household (%). The dwelling is considered overcrowded if one of the criteria mentioned below is not fulfilled: - one room for the household; - one room for each couple; - one room for each single person aged 18+; - one room for two single people of the same sex between 12 and 17 years of age; - one room for each single person of different sex between 12 and 17 years of age; - one room for two people under 12 years of age.	a. household type, b. poverty status	EU-SILC	Yes
<i>Housing costs</i>	Housing cost overburden rate	Percentage of population living in a household where the total housing costs (net of housing allowances) represent more than 40% of the total disposable income of the household (net of household allowances) (%).	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC	Yes

<i>Housing deprivation</i>	Severe housing deprivation rate	Percentage of population living in a dwelling which is considered to be overcrowded (see above), and with at least one of the following three housing situations: 1) a leaking roof, or damp walls, floors, foundations, or rot in window frames or floor (referred afterwards as 'leaking roof'), 2) neither a bath, nor a shower, nor an indoor flushing toilet, or 3) too dark.	a. household type, b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC	Yes
1.4 Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)					
	At risk of poverty or social exclusion of children (breakdown of the Europe 2020 poverty and social exclusion headline target)	People at risk of poverty or social exclusion (AROPE), expressed as a headcount or as percentage of total population. The indicator is defined as the share of the population in AT LEAST ONE of the following three conditions: at risk of poverty; in a situation of severe material deprivation; living in a household with very low work intensity.	a. household type, b. highest education of parents	EU-SILC	Yes
2. LABOUR MARKET ATTACHMENT AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE					
2.1 Labour market attachment					
<i>Employment</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Precarious employment</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Self-employment</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Unemployment</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Labour market attachment of households</i>	Children living in very low work intensity households	Share of children living in households with low work intensity (%).The indicator 'persons living in households with low work intensity' is defined as the number of persons living in a household having a work intensity below a threshold set at 0.20. The 'work intensity' of a household is the ratio of the total number of months that all working-age household members have worked during the income reference year and the total number of months the same household members theoretically could have worked in the same period.	a. household type; b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC	Yes
2.2 Work-life balance					
<i>Work and leisure</i>	Not relevant for children				
<i>Work and care</i>	Children cared for (by formal arrangements other than the family)	Share of children aged less than 3 years cared for (% by formal arrangements other than the family) as a proportion of all children in the same age group.	a. household type; b. highest education of parents, c. poverty status	EU-SILC	No
3. EDUCATION AND TRAINING					
3.1 Access to and quality of education					
<i>Early childhood education</i>	Pre-primary education enrolment	Percentage of 4 year olds who are enrolled in education-oriented pre-primary institutions (%).	-	admin	No
<i>Educational attainment</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Lifelong learning</i>	Not relevant for children				

3.2 Educational achievement					
<i>Achievement in basic skills</i>	Low reading literacy performance of pupils aged 10	Percentage of students aged 9-10 (at 4th grade) at or below the Low International Benchmark in reading (%)	a. parental education	PIRLS	No
	Reading literacy gap of low social status pupils aged 10	Difference in the average test-score in reading literacy between pupils aged 10 with at least one parent who has completed tertiary education and pupils who have at least one parent with only lower secondary education (or below)	-	PIRLS	No
	Low mathematical literacy performance of pupils aged 10	Percentage of students aged 9-10 (at 4th grade) at or below the Low International Benchmark in mathematics (%)	a. ESCS	TIMSS	No
	Low science literacy performance of pupils aged 10	Percentage of students aged 9-10 (at 4th grade) at or below the Low International Benchmark in science (%)	a. ESCS	TIMSS	No
	Low reading literacy performance of pupils aged 15	Share of 15 years old pupils who are at level 1 or below on the PISA combined reading literacy scale (%).	a. ESCS	PISA	No
	Reading literacy gap of low social status pupils aged 15	Difference in the average test-score in reading literacy between pupils aged 15 with at least one parent who has completed tertiary education and pupils who have at least one parent with only lower secondary education (or below)	-	PISA	No
	Low mathematical literacy performance of pupils aged 15	Share of 15 years old pupils who are at level 1 or below on the PISA combined mathematical literacy scale (%).	a. ESCS	PISA	No
	Mathematical literacy gap of low social status pupils aged 15	Difference in the average test-score in mathematical literacy between pupils aged 15 with at least one parent who has completed tertiary education and pupils who have at least one parent with only lower secondary education (or below)	-	PISA	No
	Low scientific literacy performance of pupils aged 15	Share of 15 years old pupils who are at level 1 or below on the PISA combined science literacy scale (%).	a. ESCS	PISA	No
	Scientific literacy gap of low social status pupils aged 15	Difference in the average test-score in science literacy between pupils aged 15 with at least one parent who has completed tertiary education and pupils who have at least one parent with only lower secondary education (or below)	-	PISA	No
<i>Early school leaving</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
4. HEALTH AND RISK BEHAVIOURS					
4.1 Health status					
<i>Objective health status</i>	Low birth weight rate	Share of new born children with low birth weight (%). As defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), an infant is considered to be of low birth weight if his/her weight at birth is less than 2 500 grams (5.5 pounds) irrespective of the gestational age of the infant.		admin	No
	Infant mortality rate	The ratio of the number of deaths of children under one year of age during the year to the number of live births in that year. The value is expressed per 1000 live births.		admin	No
<i>Subjective health status</i>	Subjective health status: fair or poor	Percentage of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who rate their health as 'fair' or 'poor' (%)	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No

4.2. Health behaviours					
<i>Physical activity</i>	Physical activity: recommended level	Percentage of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who undertake at least one hour of moderate-to vigorous physical activity a day on most days (%).	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No
<i>Obesity</i>	Overweight	Percentage of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who are overweight (pre-obese and obese) according to BMI (%).	a. age (13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No
4.3. Risk behaviours					
<i>Smoking</i>	Daily smoking	Percentage of young people aged 15 who smoke daily (%).	a. sex, b. FAS	HBSC	Yes
<i>Alcohol consumption</i>	Weekly alcohol consumption	Percentage of young people aged 15 who usually drink any alcoholic drink at least once a week (%).	a. sex, b. FAS	HBSC	No
	Heavy episodic drinking: past-30-days prevalence	Percentage of young people aged 16 consuming five alcoholic drinks or more on one occasion during the last 30 days (%).	a. sex, b. highest education of parents	ESPAD	No
<i>Illicit drugs</i>	Illicit drug use: lifetime prevalence	Percentage of young people aged 16 who have ever used any illicit drugs (%).	a. sex, b. highest education of parents	ESPAD	No
<i>Teenage birth</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Psychological distress</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				
<i>Suicide</i>	Attempted suicide	Percentage of young people aged 16 reporting suicide attempts at least once in lifetime (%).	a. sex, b. highest education of parents	ESPAD	No
5. SOCIAL CONNECTEDNESS AND CIVIC PARTICIPATION					
5.1. Family and peer relationships					
<i>Family relationships</i>	Communication with parents: mother	Proportion of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who find it easy to talk to their mothers (%).	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No
	Communication with parents: father	Proportion of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who find it easy to talk to their fathers (%).	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No
<i>Peer relationships</i>	Peer support	Proportion of young people aged 11, 13, 15 finding their classmates kind and helpful (%).	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No
	Being bullied	Proportion of young people aged 11, 13, 15 who were bullied at least once in the previous couple of months (%).	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No
5.2. Civic participation					
<i>Voting/ Voter turnout</i>	Not relevant for children				
<i>Volunteering and group membership</i>	Participation in civic activities outside of school	Percentage of students who involved in activities of any of the following organizations, clubs, or groups (%): youth organizations affiliated with a political party or union, environmental organizations, human rights organizations, voluntary groups doing something to help the community, organizations collecting money for a social cause, cultural organizations based on ethnicity, and groups or young people campaigning for an issue.	a. sex, b. parental educational attainment	ICCS	No
<i>Internet use</i>	Indicators for the 15-19 age group are included in the Youth module				

6. ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY AND PHYSICAL SAFETY					
6.1. Environmental quality					
	Noise from neighbours or from the street	Percentage of children living in households with reporting noise from neighbours or from street (%).	a. poverty status, b. severe material deprivation	EU-SILC	No
	Pollution, grime or other environmental problems	Percentage of children living in households with reported pollution, grime or other environmental problems (%).	a. poverty status, b. severe material deprivation	EU-SILC	No
6.2. Physical safety					
	Crime, violence or vandalism in the area	Percentage of children living in households with reported crime, violence or vandalism in the area (%).	a. poverty status, b. severe material deprivation	EU-SILC	No
	Self-reported neighbourhood safety	Percentage of young people who always feel safe in the area where they live (%).	a. age (11,13,15), b. age and sex, c. FAS	HBSC	No

Notes.

FAS: family affluence scale in HBSC. It is computed from four individual indicators: number of cars, having a bedroom and number of holidays and number of computers. (See for more details Currie et al. 2004: 15)

ESCS: PISA index of economic, social and cultural status. It is created on the basis of the following variables: the International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status (ISEI); the highest level of education of the student's parents, converted into years of schooling; the PISA index of family wealth; the PISA index of home educational resources; and the PISA index of possessions related to classical culture in the family home. <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=5401>

6. Recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructure and the way forward

In this report we set up the Child module of IPOLIS, based on the QoL concept elaborated in the ICP. We recall here that alike IPOLIS as a whole, the Child module also aims to serve as a resource for a wide audience: researchers, policy makers at different levels, NGO experts, journalists, students, etc. In this respect, IPOLIS is not more than an enabling tool for stakeholders to better understand social processes related to vulnerability, to stay informed, and to find empirical evidences for their questions. In a wider context, our report and the InGRID methodological and data infrastructure reports focused on other vulnerable groups are to assist the monitoring strategy of the European Commission in the field of social inclusion. These recommendations are addressed therefore to the Commission, which shall take leadership in further improving the conditions of a better monitoring system of vulnerable groups, including children. The existing monitoring framework for child poverty and social exclusion was set up by the Social Protection Committee report (SPC 2012), based on previous works related to the child mainstreaming process within the EU (e.g. Hoelscher 2004, EU Task-Force 2008, TÁRKI-Applica 2010, Belgian Presidency 2010, Frazer 2010, TÁRKI 2011).

The SPC Advisory Report to the EC on Tackling and Preventing Child Poverty, Promoting Child Well-being (2012) presented a proposal for a portfolio of child specific indicators. It adopted a holistic approach and went beyond the monetary aspects of child poverty. By taking further the policy priorities expressed by the ‘Who cares? Roadmap for an EU Recommendation on child poverty’ report commissioned by the Belgian presidency in September 2010 (Frazer 2010), the Recommendation is based on three pillars: access to adequate resources and support to households, access to quality services (early childhood education and care, education and training, healthcare, environment and housing as well as social services), and children’s participation. IPOLIS also integrates all the three pillars, albeit following a different structure (i.e. six QoL domains). There is, however, a difference between SPC (2012) and IPOLIS in the underlying approaches. In SPC *access to resources and services* is put in the forefront; while in IPOLIS both access to resources/services and performance is articulated. Accordingly, for example, IPOLIS puts a lot of emphasis on risk behaviours – an area neglected in SPC. Besides, IPOLIS attempted to go further and integrate more the pillar ‘children’s participation’.

In the selection of indicators for the Child module of IPOLIS, of the potential data sources we preferred surveys conducted in the total population or in children. Similarly to SPC (2012), we relied primarily on EU-SILC. As was seen, EU-SILC served as the main data source for the domains ‘material living conditions’, ‘labour market attachment and work-life balance’, and ‘environmental quality and physical safety’. Beside EU-SILC, a number of indicators were extracted from PISA and PIRLS for the domain ‘education and training’; from HBSC for the domains ‘health and risk behaviours’ and ‘social connectedness and civic participation’; and from ESPAD for the domain ‘health and risk behaviours’. EHIS and LFS, key sources of data in the SPC, were not used in the child module of IPOLIS, since the relatively low number of observations in the relevant age group (15-17 year-olds) may reduce the robustness of indicators.

Having noticed these differences between SPC (2012) work and IPOLIS, we provide the following recommendations to improve the monitoring of children's quality of life in the EU. When formulating our recommendations, the TÁRKI-Applica 2010 report and the TÁRKI 2011 Hungarian EU Presidency background paper serve as a starting point, which both strongly relied on the recommendations of the EU Task-Force (2008) report. Also, we acknowledge the work of Dominic Richardson (2012) prepared for the European Commission on the international surveys on children. His report, however, provides detailed recommendations to the whole stakeholder community, including not only policy makers, but also survey coordinators and researchers. Our recommendations for the European Commission are as follows.

1. Encouraging the extension of child monitoring in terms of quality of life domains and components

When setting up the Child module of IPOLIS, we found that the potential pool of policy relevant, timely, cross-country comparable and robust indicators is large and the underlying data infrastructure is rich in regard to some QoL domains (e.g. 'material living conditions' and 'health and risk behaviours'). In the case of some other domains and components (e.g. 'social connectedness and civic participation' and 'environmental quality and physical safety'), the indicator coverage and the data infrastructure are poorer. In all cases, however, we identified important gaps, indicating that there is some room to further improve the monitoring process. In what follows we list the main data gaps by domain and provide some recommendations for improving the available cross-national data on children.

Material living conditions

The domain 'material living conditions' is properly represented in the Child module of IPOLIS. We selected the most important measures out of the available pool of indicators, also taking into consideration the criteria of keeping balance across domains and components. Dynamic indicators of deprivation, as well as composite measures (beyond the existing EU2020 fight against poverty and social exclusion target) shall complete the proposed set of measures when the methodological development work will have been completed and the European Commission will have accepted them in the Social OMC portfolio.

- Survey data on material living conditions are abundant. All the information needed to compute these indicators is provided at household level, by the household reference person. This means that the same information is attached to each household member, irrespective of whether they are adults or children (even though an equivalence scale is applied to account for the economies of scale in consumption).
- One way to strengthen the child perspective would be to collect data on children's reflections to their material conditions, including financial resources, consumption and housing conditions. To some extent, the EU-SILC 2009 module and the proposal for a new material deprivation indicator touch upon this problem and make a step further, by including child-specific indicators of material conditions beside household level measures. This information is provided for all children aged 1-15 by the household reference person (basically one of the parents). Either the parent or the child is the respondent, the problems of validity and reliability of data can be raised in both cases. Present data reported by parents seem to suggest that in Europe children's material living conditions, on average, are better than those of the overall households (Guio, Gordon and Marlier 2013).

Education and training

The inclusion of the indicator of ECEC access is of major importance. ECEC services may help break the transmission of disadvantage across generations and afford all children the opportunity to reach their full potential (SPC 2012: 21). At the Barcelona Summit in 2002, the European Council set the targets of providing childcare by 2010 to at least 90% of children between 3 years old and the mandatory school age and at least 33% of children under 3 years of age, while the European Education and Training 2020 benchmark on early childhood education participation is that by 2020 at least 95% of children aged between birth and the age for starting compulsory primary education should participate in early childhood education (SPC: 2012: 22). It would highly improve the monitoring of early ages if measures of quality of ECEC, of different child developmental outcomes (e.g. physical health and well-being, cognitive skills, emotional maturity, social competence) and of family satisfaction were to complete the indicator of access to these types of services.

- According to its definition, the early school-leaving indicator is computed for those aged 18-24, which life period belongs to the youth, and thus we shifted it to the Youth module of IPOLIS. However, the indicator refers in fact to processes during childhood. At national level, there would certainly be better measures available, based on school level administrative data. These data would allow for a continuous monitoring of the drop out processes by grades. Therefore the lack of an indicator for the component 'early school leaving' is related to the comparability of national education systems and the lack of available and comparable data to provide measures that indicate or predict final drop-outs in an earlier phase of childhood. The data infrastructure related to the 'education and training' domain is relatively large and beside administrative data it includes child-centered cross-country comparative surveys. Beyond problems related to country coverage, which are discussed in more detail below, one difficulty is related to periodicity at which the relevant indicators can be produced in a reliable way. The three-year periodicity in PISA becomes in fact a nine-year periodicity when one aims to go beyond the most basic indicators: the OECD publishes regular statistics, like differences in mean test-scores according family background, only at this nine year periodicity for each of the competencies.

Health and risk behaviours

The domain 'health and risk behaviours' is one of the most documented QoL domains. Yet, some data gaps should be mentioned concerning the 'health status' and 'health behaviours' components.

- There are no data on the objective health status of children, except for the perinatal period and the first year of life;
- Only sporadic data are available on the mental health status of children. Adolescents themselves are asked about their mental health status only in ESPAD.
- Data on health behaviours (nutrition, personal care, physical activity and obesity) are available only for children aged 11 to 15 (or in case of obesity 13 to 15) from the HBSC survey, while some health behaviour patterns or problems may emerge in younger ages. This may be the case with overweight and obesity. Childhood obesity is a high priority issue and the overarching goal of the new Action Plan on Childhood Obesity¹⁸ is to contribute to halting the rise in overweight and obesity in children and young people (0-18 years) by 2020. Therefore, it is very important to better monitor overweight and obesity in childhood. Since the reliability of self-reported height and weight data is questionable, harmonised objective measurement would be more suitable for monitoring and policy intervention.

Social connectedness and civic participation

- The data infrastructure on children's family and peer relationships seems to be sufficient. However, there is a lack of data on children's relationships with others than parents or peers (e.g. members of the extended family, other adults outside of school) (Richardson 2012: 91.) Two child surveys

18 The "EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity 2014-2020" was adopted in 2014.

collect data regularly on children's relationships with their parents: HBSC and ESPAD. These surveys, along with PIRLS and TIMSS, are also the main sources of data on peer relationships. Although the formation of close attachments to family and peers has been linked to healthy youth development in numerous studies, we currently lack regular indicators on relationships with parents and peers. While indicators of family and peer relationships (the latter mainly in terms of bullying) are included in some of the reviewed child well-being indicator systems, this component of children's quality of life is neglected in SPC (2012).

- It is pronounced in SPC (2012) that children's participation in social, recreational, sporting and cultural activities is crucial to the promotion of a child's development because it enhances self-confidence as well as social and civic skills. However, as the SPC points out, the lack of systematic and comparable data on children's participation is a significant barrier to integrate this domain into the child specific poverty and well-being indicator systems (SPC, 2012: 10). Of the different forms of children's participation it is civic participation that the Child module of IPOLIS focuses on.
- Currently, the only source of data on children's civic participation is the ICCS survey. It asks students aged 13 to 14 years to state whether they participated in the activity of organizations of different kinds, including youth organizations affiliated with a political party or union, environmental organizations, human rights organizations, voluntary groups doing something to help the community, organizations collecting money for a social cause, cultural organizations based on ethnicity, and groups or young people campaigning for an issue. The first wave of the survey was conducted in 2008-2009, but up to now no information is available about the planned date of the second wave.

Environmental quality and physical safety

'Environmental quality and physical safety' is probably the domain we know the least about, with special regard to the 'environmental quality' component.

- The majority of data on local environmental quality come from household surveys (and thus asked from adults). EU-SILC provides some data on environmental pollution in the locality. The questionnaire contains one specific question about noise and one general about environmental problems. This latter question is asked about all possible complaints in the local area, including air pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry. Unfortunately, based on this comprehensive question, the environmental problem that may affect children's quality of life cannot be identified..
- There are no questions in the EU-SILC about other aspects of the locality that may affect children's quality of life e.g. green spaces, access to spaces for recreational activities, etc. As Richardson (2012) points out, questions about the local environment from the perspective of children could be strengthened including children's facilities in the area.
- Finally, indoor pollution (e.g. smoking in the home) is absolutely neglected in the surveys, however, may have harmful effects on children's health.

2. Extending child monitoring to children not or only weakly represented by the current system and the underlying data infrastructure

We recommend the inclusion of groups of children that are not captured by the present data collection, and of those that are supposed to be captured, but in fact are not fully captured. Three main issues should be discussed here.

- *Age coverage.* Children's own responses in each dimension are completely missing before the age of 9. Household surveys can be used to breakdown age-related experiences by dimension, although this information is provided by parents or guardians (Richardson 2012: 101). The lack of internationally comparable survey-derived and representative data on children under the age of 9 raises the possibility of a new international survey of pre-primary school children (Richardson 2012: 98).

- *School-based surveys.* All child-centred surveys are school-based, for which strong argument (in terms of sampling, design, financial efficiency, etc.) can be done. On the other hand, these surveys have the risk of excluding the most vulnerable. Children who are out of school (many Roma children in Europe for instance), not in mainstream school settings, are not captured by school surveys (Richardson: 98).
- *Special groups/at-risk/most vulnerable groups of children.* There are important groups of children, who are not or not properly represented in available statistics. Cross-country comparative administrative data are relatively scarce when child QoL domains are concerned and the most vulnerable groups of children (e.g. undocumented immigrants, street children) do not show up in these statistics (EU Task-Force 2008, TÁRKI-Applica 2010, TÁRKI 2011). Household surveys, as well as adult surveys collecting household level information (like the EU-LFS) also have some important shortcomings as the full coverage of children is concerned. In general, the sample realization of these surveys tends to be biased against both tails of income distribution, but especially the lower one. Children in private households at high risk of social exclusion, like those having migrant background, being travellers or of Roma ethnic origin, might be underrepresented in such surveys due to this bias. Even if they participate in the survey, a relatively large share of them cannot be properly identified (hard-to-identify groups). In a few Member States, specific information systems (based on administrative/registers data or surveys) on children in vulnerable situation exist (EU Task-Force 2008: 72).

Further, the sampling frame includes private household only and usually is taken from population registers of which up-to-datedness and reliability may greatly vary across countries. This procedure excludes not only the already mentioned vulnerable groups of children, but institutionalised children as well.

3. Supporting Member States to participate in international child surveys to promote full country coverage in certain QoL domains

Surveys, which are at the base of child-centred, non-material and outcome indicators for domains ‘education’, ‘health and risk behaviour’, and ‘social connectedness and civic participation’ are not part of the ESS (with the exception of PISA). The whole child monitoring process would benefit if the European Commission were more strongly involved in these data collections in order to improve country coverage and harmonisation in background variables.

PIRLS and TIMSS are relatively weak in country coverage. Some countries are missing (like Bulgaria, Estonia, Greece and Cyprus in the 2011 wave of TIMSS; Estonia, Greece, Cyprus, Latvia, Luxembourg, in the 2011 wave of PIRLS), and in a few cases (like Belgium or the United Kingdom) countries are represented by only one (Flanders for Belgium in TIMSS and Wallonia in PIRLS) or more (England and Northern Ireland for the UK in both surveys) regions, implying an obvious restriction to the comparability of results. We should mention here that the EU Member States-coverage of these surveys has improved during their lifetime and even compared to the previous waves in the mid-2000s. PISA has an almost full coverage of the EU Member States, only Cyprus and Malta are missing from the survey.

Neither the health and risk behaviour surveys, namely the HBSC and the ESPAD, provide full coverage of the EU Member States. In the HBSC, Belgium and the UK are represented by regions: French and Flemish parts of Belgium, and England, Scotland and Wales, respectively. In the case of the ESPAD, Belgium was represented by Flanders, while Germany by 5 Bundesländer.

Finally, as was mentioned above, the ICCS, the only survey on children’s civic participation, covers only 22 Member States.

4. Supporting the harmonisation of socio-demographic and socio-economic items in international child surveys to better account for the social gradient in child outcome indicators

First, following the implementation plan presented in the ICP, we strongly recommend that the following breakdowns be applied in each case where relevant: (i) sex, and (ii) social background. The latter is indispensable if we aim at reflecting on the differences in outcomes according to the socio-economic status of individuals, parents or households. We also suggested for consideration in each and every case the (i) age in those cases when age sub-groups represent markedly different stages of life cycle from the point of view of the indicator (e.g. young people's employment rates for those aged 18-24 and 25-29); (ii) household structure: number of household members, household type, number of parents or children; (iii) the labour market position: e.g. employment status at individual level, work intensity at household level; (iv) migrant status. In the Child module,

- for household level, EU-SILC based indicators, we included household type, highest education of parents, poverty status and work intensity status, where relevant (for example, obviously, work intensity status was not used for the low work intensity indicator);
- for survey-based indicators in the domain 'education', the economic, social and cultural status index is applied, which is supplied by the data owners on each of the three surveys (PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS);
- for child-centered indicators of health and risk behaviour, as well as of social connectedness and participation, providing age and sex breakdowns is a baseline: in the case of the HBSC-based measures the age breakdown is provided separately where relevant, but the main breakdown is the one jointly provided for age and sex; in addition, the family affluence scale index is also provided. In the case of the ESPAD survey, sex and FAS, while in the case of the ICCS sex and parental education are provided separately.
- In his recommendations, Richardson puts a strong focus on the harmonisation of socio-demographic and socio-economic measures (Richardson 2012: 111-113). For the socio-demographic measures he suggests age, sex, family form and migrant status to be harmonised across child surveys. Among socio-economic measures to be harmonised, he lists deprivation, parental education and parental employment.

We would strongly carry further Richardson's recommendation, by proposing to the EC to facilitate the coordination across the relevant surveys, also in order to make these breakdowns compatible with its own statistical requirements. While sex and in a way or another age are available on all of the surveys, family form and social-economic items are more problematic. Parental education and parental employment are present in all major surveys, excepting PIRLS, although the latter is less used and should be harmonised as an indicator. In the case of composite indicators of socio-economic status or of child deprivation, harmonisation is more difficult to achieve.

5. Strongly considering the launch of a sustainable and good quality longitudinal data collection in the Member States

Previous works in the field, which formulated recommendations on the data infrastructure (EU Task-Force 2008, TÁRKI-Applica 2010, TÁRKI 2011) stressed the importance of panel data. Even if the overwhelming majority of the indicators to monitor children's QoL are drawn from cross-sectional data, longitudinal surveys or individual level anonymised administrative data could have a remarkable value added. On the one hand these data can contribute to the indicator development process by establishing causal relationship between resources or inputs in early life stages and outcomes in later childhood or in adulthood. On the other hand, this contribution can be direct by providing specific indicators for monitoring. The longitudinal database of the EU-SILC, relying on a rotating design is an important tool in this respect, but has very strong limitations and can be used only to get better indicators on the resources side (e.g. persistent at-risk-of poverty rate). The four-year time period for which one quarter of the sample can be followed, is too short to link inputs with outcomes. It should be made clear that analysis of the long-term development of children and monitoring of truly

outcome-based indicators both require monitoring over a far longer time period than could ever be offered by the rotating panels of EU-SILC (TÁRKI 2011: 106). For the moment, only a few national level cohort studies (for examples see EU Task-Force 2008: 73) and household surveys (e.g. the German Socio-Economic Panel Survey or the British Household Panel) are able to provide an opportunity for such analyses. In many cases, longitudinal datasets are linked to administrative/register data, which provides a powerful tool to measure the long-term impacts of childhood on later outcomes and to study the mechanisms of intergenerational transmission of poverty (EU Task-Force 2008: 73-74). Their scope and validity is restricted, however, and cannot assist national level policies in other countries - even though their extensive use provides important, indispensable and partly generalizable research outcomes, also suitable for policy action.

Undoubtly, building, maintaining and using longitudinal data is costly and therefore a cost-benefit analysis should be needed (EU Task-Force 2008: 74). The European Commission has already taken action in this field by funding a pilot project for a longitudinal data collection among children, called MYWEB under the 7th Framework programme.¹⁹ The aim of the project is to assess the feasibility of a European Longitudinal Study for Children and Young People.²⁰

¹⁹ <http://www.mmuperu.co.uk/projects/measuring-youth-wellbeing-myweb>.

²⁰ For more details see the presentation of Christopher Fox (Manchester Metropolitan University) at the [expert workshop](#) on *Framework and methods for indicator building for various vulnerable groups*, held in Budapest, on 27-29 November 2013.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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